

D1.2 Families_Share mobile-based services definition

**WP1 – Conceptual framework for users' engagement,
needs' analysis, behavior analysis strategy and co-design**

30.08.2018

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Executive Summary

This document reports on the activities conducted in WP1 as part of Task 1.3 (“Definition of the Families_Share online and onsite services through co-design”) related to the design of the Families_Share platform and mobile-based services. In particular, inputs provided by stakeholders and local communities’ needs emerged through the co-design approach - described in D1.1 - have been synchronized and worked out to provide a concrete input for mobile-based services design and implementation to be conducted in WP2. This deliverable provides:

- an analysis of existing digital applications for childcare management and group time scheduling;
- a description of three usage scenarios related to the three main types of childcare activities that have been identified starting from inputs collected in T1.2. and T1.3, namely *regular childcare*, *flexible childcare* and *last minute childcare*;
- the results of a collaborative exercise performed by the project partners of the Cokido application, in order to get a general overview and a first-hand experience of a collaborative process for shared childcare through a digital service;
- the elaboration of a task flow maps, starting from the refinement of user needs and platform functionalities elaborated in during the international meeting in Limassol (Cyprus) in June 2018;
- the refinement and prioritization of user requirements and the related visual wireframes, including indications for the UX (User experience) and UI (User interface) design - as a result of the “design sprint” workshop conducted in Venice in July 2018.
- the overall documentation describing the visual identity, high-fidelity wireframes and the interaction flow that will guide the development of the first release of the Families_Share platform, as part of WP2. Mockups, wireframes and interactive prototypes of the Families_Share platform have been elaborated to detail and showcase the features and the interaction that should be supported within the application. This documentation provides a basis of communication and source of clarification that will guide the platform and mobile services development in WP2.

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1. Introduction

The design of an innovative collaborative platform and of mobile-based services to support parents in organizing collaborative childcare has a central role in the Families_Share project. As part of WP1, activities conducted in Task 1.3 - in strong synergy with activities done in Task 1.2 - had the main goal to provide a concrete input for the first release of the platform and mobile-based services design and implementation.

Following the co-design process conducted in the CityLabs, described in D1.1., this document depicts the activities conducted to define the requirements and service functionalities to be implemented in the first release of the Families_Share platform. Use cases, wireframes and interactive prototypes have been elaborated to guide the development process of services to be conducted in WP2 “Platform Development”.

Figure 1: WP1 tasks and their connection with WP2 and WP3

The needs analysis described in D1.1 has taken place in the 6 EU cities where participatory needs analysis, co-design and co-creation processes were set up (WP1). These activities lead to the development of the first Families_Share Platform prototype (WP2) which will trigger socially innovative models for socialising childcare in urban neighbourhoods (WP3).

The Families_Share methodology is grounded on a perspective of innovation as the the result of a co-production of different local stakeholders and communities involved in the project. As such, innovation is the result of a continuous negotiation between the requirements emerging from citizens and community engagement and opportunities and constraints imposed by the iterative approach that will be pursued, thanks to the re-use of an available ICT platform and the evaluation of how users will use and adapt the technology into their daily routines. In this perspective, technology is designed and shaped not only throughout the design process, but it is also reshaped through concrete and local use. Therefore, new

requirements will be derived by observing how technology is appropriated in real contexts of use —that is, how technology is refined and shaped to meet users’ local and contextual needs. This focus on the appropriation process allows us to consider mutual adjustment between the technical side and the social side. These aspects are reflected in the fact that the co-design will continue in WP3 piloting activities by investigating scaffolding strategies for the citizens to “appropriate” the technology and to integrate it in their daily life (See Figure 2).

Figure 2. The iterative design lifecycle followed in Families_Share

The goals of the design activities carried out at months 6-8 of the project, as part of WP1, were the following:

- **Analysis of existing applications.** Advancing the benchmarking process started in D1.1, we further investigated technological platforms and digital services for supporting collaborative activities, group coordination and time-management.
- **Elaboration of use cases and technology scenarios.** Starting from input gathered in T1.2 and described in D.1.1 we elaborated usage scenarios to better showcase and define possible usage of the Families_Share platform in the different CityLabs.
- **Collaborative evaluation of the Cokido application.** Since Families_Share service is grounded on the Cokido platform, a systematic analysis of Cokido functionalities and interaction modalities was carried out for better define requirements and functionalities.
- **Elaboration and definition of the design specifications.** The present deliverable includes a description of the design specification for the development of the first release of the Families_Share platform. The specification includes a description of the visual identity of the platform, details of the graphical user interface and specifications of interaction patterns. The

document is accompanied by a number of wireframes, graphical mockups and interactive prototypes that showcase the design specifications. The specifications will serve to guide the implementation activities to be conducted in WP3.

1.1. Intended audience

This document targets Families_Share consortium members in order to progress on the finalization of the design and the implementation of the first release of the Families_Share platform. It also contributes to the overall dissemination of the activities and the results of the project.

1.2. Document structure

The document is organized as follows.

Section 2 presents a detailed analysis of relevant digital platforms and mobile applications for supporting collaborative activities, group coordination and shared time-management.

In **Section 3**, the main usage scenarios for Families_Share platform are described. These scenarios represent a reference point for the conceptualization of the service design. Moreover, the section describes a collaborative activity carried out by the project partners in order to get a first-hand experience on the use of the Cokido online application.

Section 4 introduces an organized list of the needs collected and elaborated from a project meeting in Limassol (Cyprus). The section describes a first list of functionalities that emerged from the co-design workshops at the different CityLabs and presents a task flow of the main activities that might be supported with the digital platform.

Section 5 presents the first elaboration of the design specifications as they were collaboratively developed during a second project meeting in Venice (Italy). This process led to the creation of a list of requirements to be used as reference for the platform development. Moreover, this section includes a first set of wireframes and low-fidelity prototypes on the main functionalities of the mobile application.

Finally, **Section 6** describes the document specifications, including suggestions for the visual identity, GUI (graphical user interface) appearance and interaction patterns. The specification includes also an organized user flow wireframe, detailing each section of the online platform.

2. Analysis of existing digital platforms and applications

As a first step for the design of the Families_Share platform, we refined the understanding of the advantages provided by existing collaborative platforms. Part of them have been described in D1.1 (Section 3.3) as the mapping exercise conducted as part of Task 1.1 actually provided a number of guidelines that could support the design of the platform. We further refined this analysis, taking into consideration platforms and services that, even if not related to childcare, could give us input for designing specific functionalities, such as time-management or groups management features. We first present in Section 2.1 a detailed analysis of collaborative platforms that includes features related to group management. Then, in Section 2.2, we present the analysis of digital tools that can support collaborative time and shifts managements supporting members of a group.

2.1. Collaborative platforms and applications

The benchmark analysis started with the review of popular mobile applications and collaborative platforms for sharing goods and services, including childcare activities. Most of these digital platforms include sharing economy platforms based on peer-to-peer exchanges. In the next subsection we report the output of the analysis of six platforms for sharing goods and services (*Peerby* and *ShareTribe*) and childcare activities (*Yoopies*, *Bsit*, *PARC* and *Cokido*).

2.1.1. Peerby

Mobile </p>	
<p>Website: www.peerby.com</p>	
<p>Screenshots (web app)</p>	

Useful features: Through the platform, users can search and explore items exchanged or rented by people in their neighbourhood. Users can also post a request to other members of their neighbourhood if they need a particular item. Users can set preferences in the number of requests or calls that they can receive during a day.

2.1.2. ShareTribe

Description:

ShareTribe is an online platform and a mobile app that allows the creation and customization of a website marketplace online, where users can rent or sell goods, locations or services (including services for childcare). The Sharetribe company is based in Finland and its platform is available in 15 countries.

Website: www.sharetribe.com

Screenshots (web app)

Useful features: The platform guides the user in a step-by-step process for creating a peer-to-peer marketplace. The ShareTribe platform supports customization and personalization of the marketplace, allowing users to input all relevant information (including description, location, images) and to preview the result. These features can inform the design of the Families_Share platform interface for the community managers, supporting them in setting up and personalize the online community.

2.1.3. Yoopies

Mobile </div> </div>	
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Website: www.yoopies.com

Screenshots (web app)

Useful features: Yoopies focuses on childcare activities but also includes also supports for tutoring, housekeeping, senior care and pet sitting. Considering childcare, the platform helps users in finding profiles for different needs. The system guides parents in finding a babysitter by providing information for their childcare needs. This includes different options of care: occasional, part-time / after-school, full-time, nanny share and childminder. Babysitters and childcare professionals can post their ads in the platform.

2.1.4. Bsit

	<p>Description: Bsit (formerly airBsit) is a mobile application available in France, Belgium, Luxembourg and The Netherlands. The service was launched in Belgium and it basically allows parents to connect with trusted babysitters. The service allows users (parents and babysitters) to manage invitations (receiving them or posting your services to potential clients), to check on your kids in real-time (by call or message), to rate babysitters, add them to a list of favourites, and to pay them.</p>
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The platform works upon a commission-revenue model.

 Mobile

Website: www.bsit.com

Screenshots (mobile app and promotional material)

Useful features: The platform allows assistive matching of baby sitters and families. Bsit has also an interesting feature where you can "share the care" (split babysitting costs with other families that have the same need). They try to match families based on a "family quiz" (answering questions about your parenting method). In the website, registered users can find graphical material that can be personalized for promoting your own profile on the app (<https://bsit.com/en/ambassadors/support-material>). Furthermore, Bsit offers a service dedicated to companies in order to make collaborators' life easier. The app can actually be co-branded with companies.

2.1.5. PARC

Description:

PARC is a local social network for parents to arrange social activities with other friends with children. The application allows users to share events, to see which of their friends are available and to contact other parents to meet up and organize carpooling. The application is developed in Belgium and it is also available in Germany.

 Mobile

Website: www.parcapp.be

Screenshots (mobile app)

Useful features: PARC support parents in organising activities with children, allowing to invite other parents and children to these activities. Users can find activities organised by other parents (if they are public) and join them. Parents can also find child-friendly venues that are close by a location. Registered users can assign more than one children’s profile to their accounts, link them with a second parent and with friends of the child(ren).

2.1.6. Cokido

Mobile </p>	
<p>Reference: www.cokido.org</p>	
<p>Screenshots (web app)</p>	

Useful features: The Cokido online platform allows users to create or join groups and to manage activities. The platform integrates a section for organizing activities collaboratively. Parents can discover activities or propose new ones. They can also participate and sign their availabilities and needs in an interactive timetable. The platform displays also information such as the description of the activity, costs and the involvement of external babysitters. Through the interface, it is easy to assess whether an activity reached the required number of volunteers for different time slots.

2.2. Digital applications for group coordination and group time-management

The benchmark analysis included a review of popular mobile and web application for group coordination and time-management. These applications support users in scheduling meetings (*Google Calendar*), planning events collaboratively (*Doodle*) and managing time (*Monday*). These applications provide features, such as accessing shared calendars, scheduling and managing activities, tracking events and availabilities, that are highly relevant to the Families_Share mobile app.

2.2.1. Google Calendar

<p>Google Calendar</p>	<p>Description: Google Calendar is the time-management and scheduling calendar service developed by Google and offered as Google app both on the web and on a dedicated mobile application. It allows to manage events, reminders and it can be integrated with other Google applications such as Gmail.</p>
<p> Mobile </p>	

Reference: www.calendar.google.com/calendar

Screenshots (mobile app)

Useful features: Google Calendar includes many features for tracking and managing time events. For each event, users can include description, location and invite other people. The interface allows to view the events in a calendar using multiple view options: month, week, 3-day, day or schedule. The latter shows all the events in a long list, ordered by time. The application permits to manage multiple calendars. A calendar can be shared with selected people or make it public. Users can import events and calendars from external applications (e.g. MS Outlook or iCal), and export personal calendars in different formats. This application includes features that might be relevant for event scheduling in the Families_Share application, for example different views (“calendar” and “schedule” view) for visualizing time events, the steps for creating a new event, the interaction patterns that allow users to select time and dates.

2.2.2. Doodle

Description:
 Doodle is an online calendar tool for time management and coordinating meetings. Through the app, users can propose dates and time slots while the platform enables other users to vote and add their availabilities. Options such as the type of polls and answers required can be selected through the application. Doodle works primary on a dedicated website, but a mobile application is also available. The company is based in Zurich and the service is available in 26 countries.

 Web

 Mobile

Reference: www.doodle.com

Screenshots (web app)

Useful features: Doodle is an example of collaborative time scheduling, in which users can input their availabilities and find the most convenient time for all. Features related to time scheduling are highly relevant for the Families_Share platform. For example, through the Doodle platform, users can create a poll, providing description of the activity, location and tentative time slots. The users can select a time range from a calendar (monthly or weekly view) and edit specific time slots for different days. Once the dates and time slots are defined, the poll can be shared to the participants via email or with a dedicated link. Participants can express their availability and check in real-time the availabilities posted by other participants. While the poll is running, the interface shows the most voted date. Users can also export the poll with participants' availabilities to MS Excel or PDF.

2.2.3. Monday

Description:
 Monday.com (formerly dapulse) is a visual project management tool that helps groups to organize themselves and collaborate. The tool is flexible and versatile and can be used in different contexts. Basically, it consists of a table that users can collaborative edit for different purposes such as time tracking, project scheduling, event planning or task management. Other functions include file sharing and communications among members of the same project.

Reference: www.monday.com

Screenshots (web app)

Useful features: Monday.com is a tool that allows user to create tables, including time plans. Users can define days and time slots (not necessarily the same for each day), and collaboratively edits the content including defining, in a tabular view, the details of the activities for each time slot. Monday.com can be also used to collect availabilities and to get a detailed overview of time allocation among members of the same group. These features can be supported in the Families_Share application, facilitating users and group administrators in getting an overview of availabilities and participation to the different activities.

3. Scenario and usage domain consolidation

According to the input of the activities conducted in Task.1.2 and the collection of user needs, it emerged that three main scenarios should be supported through the Families_Share platform, that are related to the different types of childcare activities that were rated as highly relevant to the project.

Scenarios - as also described in D1.1. Section 4.3.1. - are stories of people undertaking activities/interactions in a given context (Carroll, 2000). Scenarios usually represent in a narrative or visual form the following element:

- user's goals and motivations
- tasks that need to be accomplished
- interactions (social + mediated)
- a specific context (temporal, spatial, cultural)

In the co-design activities described in D1.1., scenarios were used to explore with parents and stakeholders potential uses of technology and to reflect on opportunities and criticalities offered by digital solutions, therefore providing a stable foundation for action-oriented reflection (Carroll, 2000).

At this stage of the design process, we exploited scenarios to refine the understanding of the different childcare activities that emerged as relevant in the different CityLabs. Scenarios are often used to represent

the (future) interaction between users and the system and exploited as communication tool within teams in order to easily communicate, negotiate and validate system requirements.

We describe in the next section scenarios related to three main types of childcare activities that have been identified starting from inputs collected in T1.2. and T1.3, namely *regular childcare*, *flexible childcare* and *last minute childcare*. These three types of activities differentiate for the type of planning needed, for coordination mechanisms and possibly for the number of people engaged in setting-up these activities. We describe the three scenarios in the following sections.

3.1. Classification of childcare activities and scenarios description

3.1.1. Regular (routinely) childcare activities

Regular (routinely) childcare activities happen regularly for some time, like organizing a trip to the swimming pool every Monday, or agreeing on a regular division of tasks for arranging a carpool to school or pick up locations.

Scenario description and use case: Carpooling to school

A typical routinely activity implies dropping off and picking up children to and from school. Every year, during the school period, parents need to coordinate their job's schedule with the school's one which are typically not aligned. This activity becomes more complex when parents have more than one child.

According to the interviews carried out during Task 1.2, many parents tend to arrange the above mentioned tasks by coordinating with their children's classmates and living in the same area/neighbourhood.

Parents at school ABC are considering to start to carpooling their children between home and school. Parents meet at the school and as they start trusting each other they also start helping each other for drop offs and pickups. Coordination happens mainly via face-to-face meetings (at school) and WhatsApp groups and it is often weekly based. Parents usually take the children to/from school by walk or by car. This usually involves small groups of parents with around 3-4 children all together. There might be a rotation and every parent plays her/his part equally, but in case some parents have more free time than others then parents' contribution might be different. Parents who take back children from school usually around 4/4.30 pm often keep them for the whole afternoon so that children can play together. Parents take children at home or at the park or in other places (e.g. play centres or libraries), or after-school recreational or sport activities, and they share information on schedules, locations and activities carried out with the other parents through WhatsApp groups. The typical mutual help group is formed among parents whose kids are classmates at school and share the same sport or after-school activity. WhatsApp groups are used also for communicating last minute changes/needs. For instance, a parent is not available anymore to pick children up from school and she/he communicates it through WhatsApp, in order to have a fast feedback from other parents. Moreover, parents share pictures of the children during the afternoon's activities with the other parents. In the case of sport activities, the group can be activated to facilitate participation to games and tournaments during weekends as well so that one parent is mobilized to accompany small groups of kids, the exact number depending on the age group. Parents of children who attend also sport/cultural activities usually also have separated/additional WhatsApp groups with parents of children attending the same activities and living in the same area.

3.1.2. Flexible (seasonal) childcare activities

Flexible (seasonal) childcare activities are organized once in a while and have a greater degree of freedom in when and how to do them. In this case, groups have to negotiate a proper location for the childcare activities, as well as the more suitable period in which the activity will occur, taking into consideration the needs of parents and their availability in sharing their time.

Scenario description and use case: Summer activities

Examples of flexible activities are the organization of a week-long summer camp in August, planning an after school camp for the Easter holidays or organizing a Summer Lab for employees' children in an organization. These activities are usually related to a seasonal event such as holidays or national events. As part of Task 1.2 and Task 1.3, tools and strategies used by group of parents to organize flexible (seasonal) childcare activities have been identified. For instance, in Venice CityLab, the Local Church Groups regularly organizes every year, in June, a 2 weeks Summer Camp ('GREST') in Giudecca and Venice. The "GREST" is a widespread model throughout northern/central Italy based on the cooperation of parents contributing with their time, the Church making playgrounds and rooms available and volunteers (mostly teenagers/boys-girls scouts). The whole group collaborates in setting up and managing a variety of educational and recreational activities for the kids, 5 days per week and on a full time schedule.

Every year approximately 100 kids (primary school age) take part to the summer camp in Giudecca-Venice, while around 60 parents are involved in the organization of the activities with a core group of around 10/12 persons. The parents of enrolled kids join a WhatsApp group and are informed and asked for time to share, both for running workshops (from carpentry to cooking, painting, dance, English, coding, sports, etc.) and for logistic or cleaning tasks. Every day between 8-10 classes are run.

Organization activities start in February, first via face to face meetings and then two parents take the role of collecting parents' availability through a dedicated WhatsApp group and bilateral meetings/calls and composing a complex calendar puzzle on an excel sheet (see Figure 3).

Each table of Figure 3 regards a single of the GREST camp day which is divided in six moments (welcoming, initial activities, morning laboratories, lunch, afternoon laboratories, cleaning). For every moment the responsible parents are indicated, and for the laboratories sections the name of the laboratory and the name of the parent who is running it are specified.

The managers also provide a sheet summarizing all the activities for all parents. Throughout the summer camp, the WhatsApp group is used to solve emergencies (parents withdrawing from shifts and asking to be replaced) as well as to share other logistic information, and plenty of pictures.

GREST 2018 - Calendario attività

PRIMA SETTIMANA

LUN 11/6 (referenti: Novella - Silvia - Francesca)

Mattina (8:15-9:30)	Accoglienza e preparazione:						
	Novella	Giuliana	Maria	Silvia	Francesca	Valeria	
(9:30-10:30)	Lancio della danza, film e parte seria						
(10:30-12:00)	Formazione delle squadre, gioco di avvio e consegna magliette						
animatori adulti	Giuliana	Silvia	Francesca	Daniele	Christopher		
animatori ragazzi							
Pranzo	Giuliana	Roberto	Silvia	Francesca	Daniele	Novella	
Pomeriggio (14:30-16:00)	Laboratori						
referenti x lab:	Danza	Origami	Macchiette caffè	lab spinner	lab pittura maglie/borse	Giardinaggio *	
aiuto lab adulti	Novella	Isabella	Giustina	Lele	Claudia	Alessandra	Frate
aiuto lab ragazzi		Monica	Ravi		Santin	Francesca	
(16:00-17:00)	Pulizie						
	Silvia	Rossella	Bottero				

MAR 12/6 (referenti:)

Mattina (8:15-9:30)	Accoglienza e preparazione:						
	Roberto	Adriano	Rossella	Liri	Stefania	Maria	Valeria
(9:30-10:30)	Attività formative: film, preghiera, canto						
(10:30-12:00)	Dragon boat + laboratori:						
referenti x lab:	Teatro	Disegni e pitture	Basket*	Pigolte	Arte	Dragon Boat*	Giardinaggio *
aiuto lab adulti	Adriano	Martina	Luca	Anna	Veronica	Elena	Frate
aiuto lab ragazzi				Giustina		Daniele	Stefania
Pranzo	Veronica	Novella	Elena	Adriano	Silvia	Stefania	Roberto
Pomeriggio (14:30-16:00)	Giochi						
animatori adulti	Francesca	Silvia	Elena	Silvia	Laura		

Figure 3. Excel file used by a group of parents in Venice for planning their availabilities for a summer activity

Similarly, in the “corporate” case study (addressed in the Trento CityLab, see D1.1. Section 4.2.5), it emerged that the working group “0-100” - composed by employees and HR staff - uses a file Excel to plan and organize activities, to collect employees’ availabilities to volunteer for the laboratories, to find a proper location for running the activities and related support material (e.g. colours, paper, etc.).

Similarly, in the Kortrijk De Stuyverij CityLab, groups of parents self-organize exploiting Excel files for planning and coordinating shared childcare. It is worth noting that parents first look at the most suitable period for planning childcare, looking at parents needs and availability (see Figure 4). Once they select the period, they start organizing childcare activities (see Figure 5).

Opvang zomer 2018: ouders en extra's Childcare summer 2018: Parents & extra's																																		
WAT IS DIT? Vul in onderstaand schema in op welke dagen je zelf voor opvang kan zorgen. Dat wil zeggen dat je op die dag kan zorgen dat een ouder aanwezig kan zijn. Op basis hiervan kunnen we dan al een voorlopig planning opmaken. Aanpassingen in de planning zijn later uiteraard nog mogelijk. Belangrijk: vul indien mogelijk liefst meerdere dagen per week in. Uiteraard zorgen we er dan in de definitieve planning voor dat je maar één keer per week ingepland wordt.																What is this? In the document beneath, fill in for which days you can participate in the childcare. This means that 1 of the parents can be there on that day. Based on this, we can make a temporarily schedule. Future adjustments are ofcourse still possible. Important: if possible, fill in multiple days / week. We ofcourse will make shure you only need the provide childcare 1 day / week in the final schedule.																		
HOE INVULLEN? Vul jullie namen samen in op één lijn. Vul dan in de vakjes ernaast (per dag) één van de volgende cijfers in: 0 = ik kan geen opvang voorzien 1 = ik kan wel opvang voorzien 2 = ik kan wel opvang voorzien en wordt liefst op deze dag ingepland																How to fill this in? Fill in your name on 1 line. In the cells to the right, fill in (/ date) one of the following numbers: 0 = I cannot provide childcare 1 = I can provide childcare 2 = I can provide childcare and would love to be scheduled this day																		
		Juli					Juli					Juli					Augustus					Augustus					Augustus							
Naam ouders		9	10	11	12	13	16	17	18	19	20	23	24	25	26	27	6	7	8	9	10	13	14	15	20	21	22	23	24	27	28	29	30	31
Parent name		1	1	0	1	2	1	1	0	1	2	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1

Figure 4. Excel file used by a group of parents in Belgium for planning the calendar for a childcare summer activity

Opvang zomer 2018: kindjes Childcare summer 2018: Kids																															
WAT IS DIT? Vul in onderstaand schema in op welke dagen je voor je kindje(s) opvang nodig hebt. Op basis hiervan kunnen we dan al een voorlopig planning opmaken om te weten hoeveel kindjes op welke dagen aanwezig zullen zijn. Aanpassingen in jullie planning zijn later uiteraard nog mogelijk.																What is this? In the document beneath, fill in for which days you need childcare for your kids. Based on this, we can make a temporarily schedule that lets us know how many kids will be there on the specified days. Future adjustments are ofcourse still possible															
HOE INVULLEN? Vul jullie naam, en die van de op te vangen kindjes in op één lijn. Eén kindje per lijn. Vul dan in de vakjes ernaast (per dag) één van de volgende cijfers in: 0 = geen opvang nodig 1 = misschien opvang nodig (ik weet het nog niet) 2 = opvang nodig																How to fill this in? Fill in your name & that of your child on 1 line. 1 child / line. In the cells right to the name, fill in (/ date) one of the following numbers: 0 = no need for childcare 1 = maybe, I don't know yet 2 = need for childcare															
		Juli					Augustus					Augustus																			
Naam ouders	Naam kindje	2	3	4	5	6	20	21	22	23	24	27	28	29	30	31															
Parent name	kid name	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	0	0	0	0	0															
Parent name	kid name	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2															
Parent name	kid name	2	1	1	2	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0															
Parent name	kid name	1	1	1	1	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	1															
Parent name	kid name	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	0															
Parent name	kid name	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	0															
Parent name	kid name	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	2	0	0	0	0															
Parent name	kid name	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	2	0	0	0	0															
Parent name	kid name	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1																				
Parent name	kid name	0	0	0	0	0						0	0	0	0	1															
Parent name	kid name	0	0	0	0	0	2	2	0	0	0	2	2	0	0	0															
Parent name	kid name	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	1	2	2															

Figure 5. Excel file used by a group of parents in Belgium for adding their availabilities and needs

The following scenario describes one of the most common use cases of the Families_Share platform. The platform is used by an informal group of parents for organizing childcare activities for the summer period.

Eline (42), mother and single parent of two children: Lisa (7) and Laura (10), is looking for childcare for the next summer period in July and August. The previous summer, Lisa and Laura joined a pony camp, but this year Eline wants to find an alternative that is less expensive, and which is still enjoyable and full of social activities for the children. At the local primary school in Ieper, she hears at the school gate that also other parents are looking for alternatives for arranging childcare during summer. Mark, father of Ben (7) and a playmate of Lisa, mentions that his family is using the Families_Share application for arranging childcare during the holiday periods. He explains the core timesharing principles to Eline, and says that already a group of parents of the primary school has an active group for self-arranging childcare. Mark asks the email address of Eline, and says that he will invite her to the group so that she can explore the application and try it out. In this group, they are currently arranging the childcare for the

holiday period in July, and which fits to the needs of Eline. That evening, Eline receives an email from the Families_Share application to join the “Primary school leper”, she clicks on the group and can see that there are 7 other parents in the group looking for child care in July.

Before entering the dates for which childcare is needed for Lisa and Laura in July, she completes the requested profile details. Eline enters her first and last name, a short description, contact details and address. Next, she clicks on the button “add children” to make a profile for Lisa and Laura. She enters for both children first and last name, date of birth, gender. Before finishing the profile descriptions, Eline has to download and print a separate file for completing the profile information of her children. This separate file registers info about specific healthcare issues such as medicines, allergies, asthma, epilepsy, diabetes, toilet-trained, etc. Eline has to complete this file for each child, and also has to mention her contact details, her doctor’s, and any other possible babysitters that would like to join the group. Last, she also sticks a note of the National Health Service on the document. After completing the document, she scans it and uploads it to the Families_Share application. All is set now to start co-playing with other parents in the group of the primary school in leper.

Eline searches again for the group “Primary school leper”, and in the list view, she clicks on the sign up button for the holiday period in July. Her request is now being checked by the administrator of the group. Charlotte, who is the administrator and starter of the group, receives the request and accepts it. Charlotte was already notified by Mark through WhatsApp that a new parent at the school was looking for childcare in July through Families_Share. When Charlotte created this group in Families_Share for the primary school, she named the group “Primary school – leper”, and added a short description, website link to the school, and the address. Before she did this, she and other parents from the group talked with the school principal about the usage of the classrooms for child care activities, and followed the manual to prepare everything related to the insurance.

Charlotte manages all the holidays periods for this group, and also created the calendar for July, and filled in certain variables: number of co-playing days, maximum number of children per parent on one day (which is set standard at three), and time and ending time of the co-playing day. Charlotte will also organize a meeting with all parents before the start of the holiday period in order that all parents get to know each other, and can discuss further arrangements and practicalities.

In the meantime, Eline further explores the application, and sees in the communication stream several messages and uploaded pictures of previous co-playing moments organized with the group. She sees that one of the parents in the group organized an autumn workshop, whereby the children made paintings and art works out of collected green, red, and brown leaves and nuts which they collected in the forest nearby the school. She also sees another message whereby parents are requested to always foresee snacks for the co-playing dates, preferably healthy fruit snacks. Further, Eline watches one more time the explanatory video on the homepage of the Families_Share application as to know how the timesharing principle works.

A few minutes later, Charlotte approved the request to join the holiday period in July, and Eline can start marking the dates now for which she needs childcare for Lisa and Laura. The mother indicates that from Monday 6/7 till Friday 10/7, childcare is needed for Lisa, and for Laura for all dates except Wednesday as then Laura will go to her niece and aunt for a sleepover party. Next, Eline also takes her personal calendar and searches for the dates on which she might be available for co-playing as a parent. She is not available in that week from 6 till 10/7, but she has some days off in the following week. Eline indicates that she will co-play on 13/7 and 15/7, and also adds Lisa and Laura to that particular date, she also notices that she can fill in the costs that she will make for co-playing that day as a parent.

Charlotte will close the agenda when all spots will be filled in for this particular holiday period. If spots are still open, then still other families or babysitters, grandparents, or other family members can join. Just before the holiday period in July, Charlotte will also organize an informal get-together with all the parents and children to connect. For the time remaining, they will further keep in contact with each other through a WhatsApp group.

Scenarios were also elaborated in a visual form, in order to make clear some of the issues surrounding shared childcare, such as the context of use (e.g. employees working in an organization) and the interaction among participants (see Annex 1).

3.1.3. Contingency management (last minute childcare)

Last minute or “emergency” childcare activities are those activities that need to be organized to respond to unexpected or unplanned events, like, for example, in the case of strikes at schools when parents need to take care of children during working hours.

Scenario description and use case: Childcare activities in a shared space within a company

In Trento CityLab activities conducted in T1.2 provided insights on how Families_Share platform could support parents in arranging last minute childcare within organizations. In particular, opportunities given by sharing a dedicated space for childcare within the organization were discussed. In this respect, Families_Share might provide support to group of employees to arrange last minute childcare involving the use of shared spaces or resources within their organization/company. Co-design workshops organized with employees pointed out that organizing last minute childcare with colleagues also for short period of time (e.g. few hours) could be the starting point for organizing also more complex childcare activities (see flexible-seasonal childcare).

The scenario discussed and proposed by employees is the following:

It is Monday morning. Anna – an employee in the ABC organization, mother of Tim 7 y.o. – discovers that schools are set to close on Wednesday because of a teachers' strike. On Wednesday she already planned an important meeting with external visitors that she cannot postpone. She has to find a solution quickly! She talks about the strike with her colleagues during the lunch break. Jonathan, a colleague, explains that there is a dedicated room on ABC premises that employees can use to spend time with their children while they are at work. He sends an email to Anna with the link to the website where Anna will find further information of this opportunity and where she will find a calendar in order to check if this space is available. In the evening she read the email and visit the website. She also check the calendar showing the availability for the shared space for childcare. She notices that a colleague will also use this space. She thinks that maybe they could organize in turn in order to guarantee the presence of an adult while at the same time be able to participate to the meeting. The next day, Anna through the app connects with the colleague that booked the shared kids area. They decide to meet in the afternoon in the company cafeteria to know each other and understand how they can support each other.

3.2. Cokido experience

As already mentioned in D1.1. (Section 3.2), the Cokido application has a special status in the project since it is the basis upon which the Families_Share platform is designed. It was indeed crucial to the consortium partners to get the opportunity to try the Cokido application first-hand to better understand how the service works and how it can be implemented in the context of each CityLab.

After exploring user needs and the CityLabs specificities through the co-design workshops, members of the consortium participated in an exercise based on the Cokido online application to get a general overview and first-hand experience of a collaborative process for shared childcare. De Stuyverij and IMEC prepared an exercise [see Annex 2] to support the project partners in getting a better understanding of the processes (both online and offline) and features of arranging childcare through co-playing with Cokido. The exercise follows the user journey that was presented in D1.1 and describes a user scenario that was played by different members of the partner institutions. Although the scenario was fictive, it was close to reality on how groups of parents currently use Cokido, how they form a group and arrange the activity, how they

prepare the agenda, etc. The results of this experience further facilitated a shared understanding and a common knowledge on the activities that should be supported by the Families_Share digital platform.

Participants from the Families_Share consortium were divided in two groups and played the role of parents. Each group had to follow a script presenting a description of the activity of a fictive group of parents that decided to organize summer childcare activities using the Cokido approach and digital platform. The scenario included a description of the situation and a list of step that had to be followed by each participant. The exercise lasted for four days.

The main findings from the analysis of the feedback provided by the participants to the Cokido experience are reported in Table 1.

Feedback	Description
Benefits of the Cokido experience	<p>The experience helped the consortium members in exploring the Cokido platform simulating a real-world situation while playing the role of “parents”.</p> <p>The partners appreciate the overall functioning of Cokido, including features such as creating groups, inviting a person, adding personal information, creating and managing periods for childcare activities.</p> <p>Partners found that the app had a great potential and that its strong point is not only on the technological side but in combining the Cokido approach with a limited but well-designed digital support. This should be the path to be used in the design of the Families_Share application.</p>
Group size	<p>Some partners noted that the application could work better with groups with less than 25-30 members, and for activities with a limited number of timeslots (4/5 maximum). The steps required to provide some information might limit the use of the application for larger groups, and this might be problematic for some CityLabs.</p>
Homepage	<p>The homepage is one of the most important parts of the interface. Some participants were not sure on all the functions that were supported (e.g .how to search for groups).</p> <p>Some partners suggested to provide more inputs for novice users. For example, including informative material (video, images) to better understand the value of approach of sharing childcare and the steps required (the 7 steps of Cokido could be also here or when a group is opened).</p> <p>Notification of messages or other relevant information (lack of volunteers, etc.) could be displayed in the home page to trigger participants</p> <p>However, the registration, invitation and the planning process were seen as easy to follow and easy to handle. Some graphical aspects, e.g. showing all existing groups highlighted in different colours, were considered positively since they give a great overview of the variety of groups.</p>
Messages and notifications	<p>Some partners suggested to improve the message section in order to allow a more organized discussion. Some users felt that they were missing comments and input from the community, since they could not receive any notification or direct message via email.</p> <p>Partners found that the application can be an opportunity for trustful communication in closed groups which allow new members only via invitation or approval and which is further free in communicating in different languages.</p>
Location	<p>Some users noted that finding places to host activities could be a long process because options are not transparent. Therefore, additionally mapping spaces (and their qualities as well as contact person, fees, etc.) to host activities would be a useful addition for the app, in</p>

	particular with respect to certain CityLabs.
Adding availability	Adding availabilities of parents or children was one of the weak points of the Cokido application that should be reviewed in the Families_Share platform. The Cokido app requires the parents to select and confirm the availability for all time slots. Partners expressed that they would like to have a easier and quicker way to register children to the different activities. They would also require different views, for example to get an overview of all the availabilities assigned by a single user across multiple activities.
Application in other CityLabs	Considering the application of the Cokido platform to different CityLabs, the consortium partners highlighted some areas for improvement. For example, a more effective support for time-management and coordination among group members. Other partners reported that the usage of the application would need to be introduced via a local contact person (e.g. community manager) and institution which have already established trust (e.g. day care centres, schools, etc.). The development of the new platform should consider this aspect.

Table 1. Results from the Cokido experience

4. Needs refinement and task flow definition

The bases for the design of the first version of the Families_Share platform were laid out during a project meeting in Limassol (Cyprus) [described in D1.1, Section 5]. The meeting had the goals of aggregating the needs collected at the local level from the different CityLabs and to prioritize the functionalities emerged in the local co-design workshops. In the meeting, the affinity diagramming exercise pointed out many needs shared among the different City Labs, namely:

- The platform should support the creation and the management of “trusted” groups of people aimed at sharing childcare duties in several different ways; volunteering and community values are the driving forces that are recognized and should be fostered.
- There are three main typologies of activities that need to be supported: regular, flexible and possibly the last-minute or emergency activities.
- Offline encounters are important for trust building and the platform should encourage face-to-face communication and coordination.
- Support in time allocation is crucial and it should be a major functionality (or set of functionalities) in the platform.
- Management of space is critical and platform should support the group in finding, assessing and, when needed, contracting a proper location.

The main features of the Families_Share platform, presenting for each of them the main functionalities, the users involved and their role, the ending issues to be tackled during the Venice meeting, namely:

- Community configuration and set-up
- Registration
- User and children profile
- Groups creation and management
- Activity creation and management

These initial inputs have been worked out together with input described in Section 2 and Section 3 of this document in order to define the service features and to identify pending issues and critical aspects to be addressed before the implementation phase. We synthesized these in the following sections.

4.1. Features, functionalities and pending issues

4.1.1. Community configuration and setup

The configuration of the CityLabs communities should be available to adapt the platform to the different contexts in which Families_Share will be deployed.

CityLabs communities are characterized by the following features:

- Type: social vs corporate community
- Name
- Picture
- Description
- Language
- Geographic area
- Available resources (locations, agreements, insurance, access rights, etc.)
- Group management definition: for corporate community it might be that specific rules should exist for groups, that can only activate a limited number of features, while groups in “social” communities have more freedom (e.g. exchange model, reciprocity, etc.)

The community configuration is done by the community manager(s), in several contexts a team of community managers should be foreseen (e.g. In Venice and Trento: an overall team management by each partner, with a distributed model, to be flexibly interpreted, involving several individuals volunteering from the local networks, who are left with the possibility of deciding on their rules). The community manager also provides support to groups (answer questions, provide resources, support groups in managing conflicts, provides legal and insurance-related support).

Pending issues

- Consolidate the community management features.
- What is decided at the community level?
- What is decided at the group level?
- Necessary to define parameters that can be tuned when defining a community vs group?

4.1.2. Registration

The steps that a user should follow for accessing the Families_Share platform, register and participate to a group are the following:

- Download the application
- By downloading the application, the user join a specific community (social or corporate)
- Registration
 - user will need to fill the consent form and then to do the authentication
- Welcome and first highlights on the benefit of the approach, the main steps for organizing

- childcare, etc (check relevant material to trigger user participation and engagement)
- Once registered, the user can:
 - see all the resources of the community
 - search for groups or activities
 - create a new group
 - join an existing group

Pending issues

- Define which contents and information are accessible before and after the registration, e.g.: the information related to community activities are visible also for non-registered users? For example, testimonials, stories, etc.
- For “Corporate” Communities, mechanisms to manage access should be provided in order to guarantee that only the network of employees can register.

4.1.3. User and children profile

“Adult” user profile:

Profile building should be designed as incremental features where data and information are requested only if relevant, for instance

- Initial phase: only contact information: email, mobile phone, secondary phone, emergency phone, WhatsApp, address)
- “about yourself” section can be filled in different moments (when participating to an activity)

Children profile

- keep it flexible (for some countries it is mandatory to ask the gender, in other no)
- no photos
- health-related issues - only shared with parents that will take care of the child

The user profile is characterized by the following features:

- Name
- Role in the group: admin, financial, manage agenda, location, etc.
- Description: optional
- Add children profile
- Add other external volunteers (such as family members or siblings) and professional educators.

4.1.4. Groups creation and management

Groups can be created by each registered user. Groups members are registered users that can be:

- parents
- volunteers
- external paid professionals (e.g. educators, shared baby-sitters, au-pairs)

Groups can be:

- open: still looking for other members
- closed: the group is full and no more participants can enter the group.

In both case, groups can decide to be public (visible by other users) or private.

- public: some information about the group can be accessed by Families_Share users.
- not public: all information about the group are hidden to non-members

Groups are characterized by the following features:

- Name
- Description (e.g. goal of the group, which type of activity do they propose?)
- Picture
- Members
- State
 - open (other members can join) or closed (no other member can join the group)
 - visible or private
- Groups administrators
- Normal users
- Agreement on type of exchange and reciprocity model (which is the type of exchange that the group propose? Time-banking, solidarity-based where members contribute in different ways and according to their possibility).

4.1.5. Users roles

Group Administrator(s)

Groups can be created by registered users, that become “Groups administrators”

Several “Group administrators” can exist in each group, actually, the platform should encourage to identify more than one “Group administrator” in order to guarantee the group functioning.

Group administrators:

- can invite other persons to join the groups
- can change the status of the group members in “Group administrators”?
- approve the request of user to join a group
- close the group?

Group members

Group members are those who are part of a group. A user can be member of different groups. In the Cokido platform, there are five distinct roles in a group with different responsibilities (who takes care of the agenda, who takes care of the toys and other material, who manages the financial transactions, who takes care of the space and the administrator).

Pending issues

- make visible user roles (who takes care of agenda, etc?) - should the system suggest to user that they can take care of these aspects?
- Agreement: how agreements are managed by groups? Are some main aspects of the agreement visible when entering a new group? how?
- Do group members communicate through the platform?

4.1.6. Activity creation and management

Groups members (administrators and regular members) can create an “Activity”. An “activity” is incrementally designed as all the elements are found within the group (volunteers, children location, etc.) or outside the group (looking for other volunteers, space, insurance). Planning an activity requires therefore negotiation and collaboration among group members at different levels, and implies offline and online interaction.

An activity can be closed if some of the conditions required to run an activity are not met (e.g. not enough volunteers or children, lack of space, etc.).

An activity entails different types of group interaction:

- *planning*: in which period will the activity take place? how many volunteers? How many children? etc
- *coordination*: volunteers should coordinate in order to organize the activity

We can take inspiration from the Cokido experience and their approach:

- 1) selection of the time of needed childcare,
- 2) selection of the availability in providing childcare,
- 3) final planning.

The agendas of the group are closed very soon and in case of changes (upcoming unavailability of the parents) the group can fix them also, if needed, by appointing external babysitting services.

An activity is characterized by the following features:

- Name
- Description
- Type:
 - Recurrent (routine): happen regularly for some time, like organizing a trip to the swimming pool every Monday, or agreeing on a regular division of tasks for take to school and pick ups
 - Seasonal / flexible: are organized once in a while and have a greater degree of freedom in when and how to do them: like organizing a week-long summer camp in August
 - Last minute: those that need to be organized to respond to unexpected or unplanned events, like for example, in the case of strikes in schools when parents need to take care of children during working hours
- Location
- Date start- date end
- Number of volunteers involved
- Number of children involved
- State
 - open
 - planning phase:
 - looking for volunteers
 - looking for a location

- place available for more children
 - agenda definition
 - running
- closed
 - evaluation

The group can evaluate the activity in order to improve the organization of childcare activities, to learn from their experience and maybe to share this knowledge with other groups.

4.1.7. Calendar

Each group has a shared calendar/agenda as the main tool to coordinate the shared childcare activities. The calendar/agenda should have the following features:

- allow group members to join the activity (through the calendar) as an active participant
- give or not give the availability to share time for childcare
- indicate children taking part to the activity

Different approaches for supporting group coordination and planning of childcare activities were discussed:

1. the “doodle” and the “calendar” approaches consist in making visible the availability and the constraints of the different members of the group and
2. an automatic system that, after considering the availability of the individuals, assign the time slots.

The former is probably more suitable for small and medium groups, it might also support larger groups; while the latter might be more complicated but in could be necessary for larger groups.

4.2. Privacy compliance needs

In the elaboration of user and system requirements, attention has been given to privacy and data protection. A crucial issue addressed in the co-design process within T1.2 and T1.3 (described in D1.2.) and to be further explored as part of task 6.3. (Trust and safety framework) was to find an efficient solution for dealing with privacy issues and private data, in a way that allows community members to share relevant information (relevant in order to raise reciprocal trust) while at the same time protecting personal data— with particular sensitivity given to protecting data on children. In this section we summarize the needs emerged regarding privacy, differentiating between registered and non-registered users.

4.2.1. Registered users

Registered users are users of the Families_Share platform who have previously registered. They are provided with credentials and can login into the platform. Registered users can join groups and create activities. Group administrators are all registered users.

Regarding privacy concerns, the registration process necessarily provides personal information to the platform. Following the GDPR legislation, registered users can request to access any personal data gathered through the platform, they can request to export their personal data in a machine-readable format and can request to delete their personal data.

Furthermore, the consortium partners decided that sensitive information about children - as health-related data - will be disclosed to other users only when these information will be relevant for the childcare activity

(that is only once the childcare activity has been planned) and only to those users that will take care of the children. In any case, to avoid the disclosure of any sensitive information about Families_Share users and their children, an explicit consent should be asked.

4.2.2. Non-registered users

Non-registered users are users who access the application without completing the registration process or without logging into the system. Non-registered users might get access to informative content (e.g. about the Families_Share project) or browse groups that have provided their consent to share their information to the general public (for example for sharing knowledge or for looking for new members). Sensitive information is not disclosed to non-registered users.

4.3. User journey refinement and task flow representation

A first version of the user journey was detailed in D1.1. (Section 5.2). The user journey is a graphical representation used to map the relationship between a user and a service across all channels in which they interact (e.g. people, telephone, website, mobile apps, etc.). A user journey is always represented from the user perspective but also incorporates the touch-points between the service (and the organization behind it) and the user experience requirements as the journey progresses.

Based on the user journey, we defined the task flow. Task flow is a representation of the path that a user follows through an application. In our case, the task flow includes all the tasks that a user can perform through the Families_Share application, giving an overall representation of the service architecture. The task flow shown in Figure 6 has been divided in four main sections:

1. Registration and user profile
2. Creating and managing groups
3. Creating and managing activities
4. Time and availability management and scheduling

Moreover, we compared the functionalities already implemented in Cokido and checked whether the tasks listed in the Families_Share task flow were already supported (or not) in the Cokido platform.

Task flow

Figure 6. Task flow with the main elements of the Families_Share platform

5. UX and UI design

The next step in the design process for the Families_Share platform consisted in the refinement of the system and user requirements and the creation of the visual wireframes, including indications for the UX (User experience) and UI (User interface) design. To actively involve the consortium partners in this process, we adopted the “design sprint” approach (Knapp, Zeratsky, & Kowitz, 2016)

A “design sprint” is a rapid process that uses design thinking to reduce the risk when bringing a new product or service to the market. The activity is organized in “sprints” (a concept originated in the Agile method) where teams of any size are asked to solve and test design problems through the “design thinking” process, a problem solving process developed by IDEO and by the Stanford d.school (Johansson-Sköldberg, Woodilla, & Çetinkaya, 2010). These two concepts (“sprints” and “design thinking”) were adapted to the idea of “design sprints” by the Google UX teams and Google Ventures who refined and disseminated the design sprint approach (Knapp, Zeratsky, & Kowitz, 2016). In our case, we adapted the approach to quickly identify design issues and to converge on possible solutions (Figure 7).

Figure 7. The process followed in the design sprint workshop

5.1. Venice design sprint workshop

A workshop has been organized in Venice on the 18th and the 19th of July 2018. During the two-day workshop (Figure 8), partners of the consortium took part to the design sprint with the goal of defining the requirements and starting to sketch the platform interface. The sprint was based on the insights gathered through the co-design workshops conducted at the local level (See D1.1. Section 4.4), the results of the requirements prioritization process done as part of T1.3 (see D1.1. Section 5) and the first-hand experience with the online Cokido platform (Section 3.2).

Figure 8. Venice design sprint workshop

The first step in the process was the discussion and revision of the user and system requirements. This step resulted in a list of requirements that was shared with all the members of the consortium (see next section and Annex 3).

The second step in the design sprint workshop was the creation of a set of wireframes for the Families_Share application. A wireframe is a visual representation of a user interface that displays the functional elements, stripped of any visual design or branding elements. Wireframes are used for planning

a site or application's structure and functionality and for communicating what the items on that interface should be, based on the user needs. These preliminary wireframes were made by workshop participants using pen-and-paper. For supporting the creation of the wireframes, a set of wireframes from the Cokido application has been prepared (see Annex 4). In this way, participants could have a reference to start with instead of starting to design the wireframes from scratch. Examples of the wireframes created during the workshop are presented in the next section.

Lastly, after the elaboration of the results from the design workshop, the FBK team produced the graphical assets, the interactive prototypes and the final specification report for the Families_Share platform.

5.2. Results

The outputs of the design sprint workshop included a revised and updated list of requirements to be used as reference for the development of the platform, and a number of design ideas that served as a basis for the creation of the interface wireframes and interactive prototypes.

5.2.1. Requirements list, features revisions and updates

The full list of requirements is described in Annex 3. The list includes a total of 64 requirements and corresponding criticalities. The requirements are also grouped in categories (15 categories) and priority level (Low, Medium and High). The requirements were also divided in requirements to be implemented in the first release of the platform ("first prototype version") while another set of requirements were left for the second implementation cycle ("second prototype version"). The subsequent phase of the design process described in Sections 6 of this Deliverable is based on the elaboration of the first set of requirements with the goal of defining the UX and UI of the first release of the Families_Share platform.

The following Table 2 summarizes the requirement list.

Total number of requirements: 64					
Categories (not exclusive)	# of requirements	Categories (not exclusive)	# of requirements	Priority level	# of requirements
General	2	Privacy	9	High	27
Website	2	Search	2	Medium	21
Interface	3	Group management	4	Low	10
Community management	4	Communication	6		
Registration / Log-in	4	Activity management	21		
User categories	3	Notifications	3		
User profile	6	Children info	4		
Calendar	5				

Table 2. Summary of the requirements listed in Annex 3

5.2.2. Preliminary sketches and wireframes

During the workshop, participants created preliminary sketches and low-fidelity interface wireframes for rapidly communicating interaction designs and ideas. Wireframes are commonly used in Interaction Design to illustrate design concepts, visual layout, interface behaviour, and the general “look and feel” of the interaction. Wireframes usually serve to answer these questions (Cao, 2017):

- **Structure** – How will the pieces of this application be put together?
- **Content** – What will be displayed?
- **Informational hierarchy** – How is this information organized?
- **Functionality** – How will the interface work?
- **Behavior** – How does it interact with the user? And how does it behave?

SKETCH

LOW-FIDELITY
WIREFRAME

HIGH-FIDELITY
WIREFRAME

Figure 9. Sketch, low and high fidelity wireframes (examples from the design of the Families_Share platform)

Sketch and low-fidelity wireframes were created during a collaborative activity focusing on the four main functionalities supported in the Families_Share application, namely (i) registering and creating a personal profile, (ii) creating and joining groups of users, (iii) creating and joining activities proposed by group members and (iv) managing participation to these activities. This material was used as input for refining design ideas and creating high-fidelity wireframe after the workshop.

A part of the wireframes created are reported in Figure 10 and in the remaining of this section.

Figure 10. Some of the mockups and wireframes developed in the design sprint workshop

The wireframes represented some design concept as described below:

Landing Page

The landing page provides information on the group, such as scheduled activities and pending messages and notifications. The page includes a calendar and a dedicated navigation bar on the bottom.

Group page

The group page shows information on the group activity, including (i) messages and notifications, (ii) planned activities and (iii) information on the group members.

Group and activities

Group members can propose new activities by accessing a dedicated section on the application. These activities are displayed both in the calendar or in a list.

Group creation

The interface enables group administrators in creating new groups. The interface guides the user through the process, giving indications on creating the group and on inviting new members.

6. Design specification

The results of the design sprint workshop were further elaborated in order to produce the documentation describing the visual identity, high-fidelity wireframes and the interaction flow that will guide the development of the first release of the Families_Share platform, as part of WP2. In creating the wireframes for the application, we followed the Material Design principles. Material design (<https://material.io/>) is a design language developed by Google, utilized in many mobile and web applications. The benefits of adopting the Material Design language is a more consistent visual language and a faster development, since most of the interface components (buttons, menus, icons, drawers, etc.) included in the wireframes can be easily integrated while coding the mobile application.

6.1. Visual identity

The Families_Share logo represents the concept of co-creation and sharing. The four shapes depicted symbolizes collaboration and flexibility, that are attributes of the activities supported in the platform.

Inspired by the colours in the project logo, three different proposals for the online platform color scheme have been elaborated. The three proposals includes a primary and a secondary color, and their lighter and darker variations (see Annex 5).

The three color scheme have been scored in a survey filled out by Families_Share partners. The survey investigated also whether the color scheme was already used by other popular brands or digital services in the CityLab countries. The results (see Annex 5) indicate that the first color scheme (Cyan and Orange) was the preferred and more suitable one (Figure 11).

Figure 11. Color scheme chosen for the interface of the mobile application

Based on the selected color scheme, we designed an application icon inspired by the graphical elements of the project logo (Figure 12, 13 and 14). Variations of the logo for each city labs were also created since different instances of the Families_Share application will be available through the Play Store (Figure 14).

Android Legacy Icon

Figure 12. Icon proposed for the mobile application

Figure 13. Representation of the Families_Share application in Android and in the Play Store

Figure 14. Variations of the application icon for the seven CityLabs

6.2. Consolidated wireframes

The subsequent phase in the design process was to create high-fidelity wireframes for the Families_Share application. These wireframes represent the “look and feel” of the platform and can provide indications on the structure, the content and the functionalities envisioned for the application. This information can guide and direct the development process.

Considering the main activities supported in the platform and described in the user journey / task flow map (see Section 4.3), high-fidelity wireframes were designed according to the user and system requirements (Section 5.2.1 and Annex 3).

The design process that led to the creation of the wireframes was characterized by a number of iterations. The consolidated wireframes are the result of a cyclic process of prototyping, discussion, and refining and are included in Annex 6. The wireframes represent the most important functionalities in the application, including registration, user profile management, group and activity creation, scheduling and tracking. In the following section we report the list of requirements corresponding to each functionality and provide a detailed description of the UX and UI design choices represented in the wireframes.

6.2.1. Registration, user profile and privacy

The following table outlines the requirements related to registration, user profile and privacy.

ID	Requirement	Description	Group	Priority
7	User name visibility	User should be able to decide if their name should be searchable (visible / not visible)	User profile Privacy	High
8	User search visibility	Some users could decide to be invisible to the community.	User profile	High

		If they are not visible, to add them to a group or as a parent you should input the email or telephone number	Privacy	
9	Cancel profile	Users should be able to cancel all their information	User profile Privacy	High
11	Export all information	Users should be able to export all their data stored in the platform (as JSON)	User profile Privacy	High
12	Integrate children information within the platform	Children information should be provided within the app (not in a printed form) Data should be encrypted	Children info Privacy	High
13	Showing children basic information + special needs	Children basic information such as name, age and gender should be visible to the other members of the group (when organizing an activity) If there is any special needs, a symbol can be placed next to the children name Integrate child card inside the app. So that we can search e.g. based on the age of the participants of the group. Age and gender are most important info too. Perhaps also add information about possible health issues (call it "special needs").	Children info	Medium
14	Managing who can view your full children information	When users provide their children information they should be notified and accept that these information can be shared with other members of the group. Users should be able to decide who can see this info. [Information sharing option]	Children info Privacy	High
15	Export children information	Users should be able to export in a PDF file the children information of the activity they are involved	Children info Privacy	High
16	Privacy consent at the registration	When users register in the platform, the platform should make sure that consent is "informed consent" and provide necessary privacy notice and other information at the time user consent is required. The registration process stops if user do not provide the consent	Log-in / Registration Privacy	High
17	Parents can add other users as parents	Parents have different profile and their share the same children profile A parent can be added as co-parent / guardian / family member	Children info User profile	Medium
21	Single sign on	This is an optional feature. We will start with registering for a local account functionality and perhaps integrate that in the future.	Log-in / Registration	Low
37	Log-in with email	Allows log-in with email address	Log-in / Registration	High

Table 3. Requirements related to registration, user profile and privacy

According to the requirements listed in the table above, a set of high-fidelity wireframes were elaborated.

LANDING PAGE

About the project

The Families_Share project is developing a social networking and awareness-raising platform dedicated to encouraging childcare and work/life balance.

[LEARN MORE](#)

Groups in the community

- Group Star**
15 members, 13 kids
Participation to the activity is open
- Group Beta**
20 members
Participation to the activity is open
- Group Gamma**
24 members
Participation to the activity is open

In the start page, new users can

- decide to log in or sign up by tapping one of the two buttons present in the orange bar immediately below the header;
- know more about the project by tapping "Learn more";
- visualise the groups active in the community and, by tapping one of them, reading a short description.

About the project

Funded under the Information and Communication Technologies programme of Horizon 2020's Industrial Leadership component, and its call for collective awareness platforms for sustainability and social innovation, the Families_Share project is developing a social networking and awareness-raising platform dedicated to encouraging childcare and work/life balance. The platform capitalises on neighbourhood networks and enables citizens to come together to share tasks, time and skills relevant to childcare and after-school education/leisure, where these have become unaffordable in times of stagnation and austerity.

The challenge

Balancing work and family life has become increasingly challenging in the last decade in Europe.

By tapping on the orange button, new users will redirect to the registration page

REGISTRATION

Do you already have an account? [Log in](#)

Name

Phone Number (optional)

Email

Password

Confirm password

My profile appears in search results

I accept the Terms of Use and the Policy in regards to the treatment and use of my data.

[CONFIRM](#)

In order to sign up, users need to

- fill the form (by adding name, email, password and, optionally, a phone number)
- state whether they want their name appearing in search results;
- Agree to the terms of use and privacy policy.

Instead, if they are already registered, they can tap the link before the form.

[Terms of use](#)

Do you already have an account? [Log in](#)

Name
Lucia Bianchi

Phone number
+48 12345678

Label
Mobile

Email
lucia.bianchi@email.com

Password

Confirm password

My profile appears in search results

I accept the Terms of Use and the Policy in regards to the treatment and use of my data.

[CONFIRM](#)

PERSONAL AREA

Only after sign up / log in, the user is inside is personal area, where several elements can be found:

- Personal calendar: it can be expanded to show all the days where the user or his children are involved in some way;
- Personal groups: these are the groups to which the user belongs. New notifications of the group are alerted thanks to the coloured circle and the number relating to how any there are.
- Personal notifications: here there will be displayed notifications such as invites or pending requests to join a group, the admittance of a new member into one of the personal groups and, if administrators, requests to join one's group.

By tapping the hamburger menu, a navigation drawer opens, displaying several actions.

User notifications in the personal area

A registered user can receive the following notifications in the personal area:

- a new member joined a group that the user is part of;
- the state (pending, accepted, rejected) of an invite that was sent from the user to a friend;
- the invite to join a group. The invite can be sent from a group administrator to the user, offering the possibility to enter the group. The user can browse the group description presented in the "About" section and accept the invite;
- the status of a request of the user to join a group which is has not been approved yet and, thus, is still pending;
- the approval or rejection of the user to join a group from the group administrator(s);
- the request to be the administrator of a group the user is part of;
- the approval or rejection of an activity created by the user in a group;
- the notification that a parent/guardian was added to a user's children profile.

NAVIGATION DRAWER

From this navigation drawer, the user can reach several pages dedicated to the:

- personal profile;
- creation of a new group;
- search of groups;
- Invitation of friends;
- Frequently Asked Questions (FAQs);
- Information about the project.

It is also possible to sign out from the community.

FAQ SECTION

In this section, users can visualise the frequently asked questions and find answer related to several practical topics

PROFILE AND PRIVACY

The profile is divided into three tabs:

Here, information about the user are present both personal and whether he/she covers the role of group administrator. It is possible to modify the profile by tapping the pencil icon present in the upper part of the screen.

Here, the children of the user are present and, thanks to the Floating Action Button (FAB) is possible to add a child. It is possible to modify the profile by tapping the pencil icon present in the upper part of the screen.

Here, the members of the user's network of family and friends are displayed. It is also possible to invite more friends thanks to the FAB. It is possible to modify the profile by tapping the pencil icon present in the upper part of the screen.

By tapping the more icon next, a menu appears that allows to:

- Export all the data present in the profile;
- Delete all the data to preserve privacy;
- Sign out.

6.2.2. Creating and managing groups

The table outlines the requirements related to creating and managing groups within the digital platform.

ID	Requirement	Description	Group	Priority
1	Website for each community	Each community has a website as companion of the app (each CityLab can have more than one community) Perhaps we could use second level domains for these (e.g. trento.families-share.eu).	Website	High
2	Website shows the list of groups for that community (as in Cokido)	We can create an endpoint within the app that returns information about public groups. So the website could be totally static, apart from the content shown from that endpoint. That way one could browse some public groups and perhaps see photos, just like in Cokido. If they click on the group however, they will need to download the app and register.	Website	Low
3	The app has different instances	Each community will have its app to download from the Google Play Store (android first and then iOS later on)	General	High
4	App design is mobile first	The interface will be designed mainly for mobile phones but it can be access also from the web (for iOS and web users)	General	
5	Search group	Users can search for groups from the web page or from the mobile app	Search	High
18	User hierarchy	Community manager <- Group administrator <- User	User categories	High

		(parents / professionals) <- External [i.e. person not registered in the platform] This means that the community manager is inherently a Group administrator for all groups The Professional is a user role that has certain permissions.		
19	New member notification	When a new member enter a group all other members are notified	Notification	Medium
20	New member acceptance rule	Two options are provided: Strict: all members (who are also group administrators) they have to agree to the new member Flexible: at least one group administrator agrees	Group management Community management	High
22	Community default options	Options when you create a community: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New members are automatically administrator OR not • Approval for new members: Do all group administrators need to agree? Or just one is fine? (i.e. AND or OR). [see #20] Group can change this option or not	Community management	Medium
23	Community access option	The community can be open or not	Community management	Medium
24	Group settings when creating a group	A group can be visible or not visible: that is a group can be searchable or not. If it is visible, an external user can contact the group administrator for joining the group	Group management Privacy	Medium
25	Join a group with an invite	All groups are invite-only. Some are visible and some are not. If it is not visible you have to receive an invite by the group administrator to join in. If the group is visible, you can contact the group administrator to receive an invite.	Group management	High
26	Type of notifications	Members and group administrators should receive notifications. System event notifications e.g: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - "a new user entered the group" - "a new activity has been created" - "the agenda for a specific activity was closed" The notification can be sent in the phone or by email	Notifications	High
28	Professional users	Professionals can be invited by group administrators. They are users and can access information related to the activity in which they are involved OR we can keep as it is in Cokido (information provided in the activity by the group administrator)	User categories	Medium
30	Types of activities	The interface should support activities that have two characteristics: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Recurrent vs One-time - Flexible vs Fixed User should not categorize the type of activity, this can be automatically inferred by the system	Activity management	High
31	Promote groups and activity	We should provide indications or material for supporting the promotion of groups or activities (flyer, social media material, etc)	Group management Activity management	Low

34	Starting page / Homepage for new users	Information displayed to the users when they access the platform: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Login Registration form - Info on Families_Shares project - Info on active groups 	Interface	Medium
35	Starting page / Homepage for registered users	Information displayed to the registered users when they enter the application: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Calendar - Joined groups - Notifications 	Interface	Medium
36	Provide checklists	Provide users with checklists for supporting some activities (WhatsApp group creation, financial rules, etc.)	Interface	High
39	Support communication within and outside the app	Communication can be supported within the app (announcements / message) or outside (WhatsApp/telegram/facebook). This can be decided by the community manager.	Communication Community management	Medium
40	Announcements (a.k.a. Messaging) feature	Kept as they are in Cokido (basic) but call them Announcements and have it for informing group members This can include also info for support the group to manage a whatsapp / telegram group Users should be able to post message and give replies	Communication	High
41	Edit announcements / replies	You can edit announcements or replies (created by you)	Communication	Medium
42	Deleting announcements / replies	You can delete announcements or replies (created by you)	Communication	Medium
44	Images in the announcements	Announcements can include an image	Communication	Medium

Table 4. Requirements related to creating and managing groups

Based on the requirement, the following wireframes for search and create groups were elaborated.

SEARCH AND JOIN A GROUP

Before joining a group, users can have a peek into groups so as to decide whether they attract their interest by reading a short description. Therefore, in the bottom navigation menu, only the "About" section is accessible to them for privacy reasons.

If they wish to join a particular group, like the one in the picture, they can tap the button "Join Group" to request access and then await the notification of admittance in the personal area.

After tapping "Search a group" in the navigation drawer, a user can search groups by typing either its name, city or post code.

GROUP SECTION

Once a member of the group, all the four sections are equally accessible to the user thanks to the bottom navigation menu, that is:

NEWS

ACTIVITES

MEMBERS

ABOUT

GROUP - NEWS

The "News" section is composed of two tabs:

NOTIFICATIONS

The user will receive all notifications pertaining the group only, such as the creation of a new activity, the admittance of a new member...etc.

MESSAGES

Messages can be exchanged on a wide variety of topics related to the group. The FAB allows the user to write a new message.

GROUP - MEMBERS

In this section, all the group members are listed in alphabetic order. For each member it is possible to contact them either via phone or mail or both.

The administrator(s) is distinguished with a label and an orange star to denote his/her role.

In the About section, a list of cards display or link to information that could be useful to the user, that is:

- Information about the group;
- The rules of the group agreed upon by all members;
- A 7-steps start-up guide for new users.

This is the first page a newly accepted member will see when entering the group as to discover more about it. Afterwards, the first section upon access will be "News".

GROUP - ABOUT

GROUP - NOTIFICATIONS

The notifications related to a group are displayed as shown in the picture (i.e., number and circle) in the start page.

Moreover, when inside the group, a similar badge positioned on the right upper corner of the icon of the "News" section calls attention to the unread notifications.

Group notifications in group start page

These notifications are strictly related to the group activity, including:

- visualizing group rules (only present in case of first access);
- a new member has joined the group (with information on the name of the new member);
- a new activity has been created;
- the agenda of a particular activity has been closed;
- the agenda of a particular activity has been locked;
- an activity has been deleted;
- a timeslot in which the user has signed up has been confirmed / deleted;
- a new group administrator has been added.

Notification badges are present to call the user's attention to new notifications. The notification badges are displayed in the personal area (a badge for each group) and in the icon related to the "News" section in the bottom navigation menu inside a group section.

NEW GROUP CREATION

Four steps are necessary in order to create a group:

6.2.3. Creating and managing activities

The following table outlines the requirements related to creating activities.

ID	Requirement	Description	Group	Priority
45	Activities are mapped in a collection of timeslots	When you create an activity you set a time range (and this can be edited) and define time slots	Activity management	High
46	Timeslots have counters	Users should be able to mark their availabilities and their need for each timeslot Counters can represent volunteer availabilities AND needs (children)	Activity management	High
47	Propose different activities	Users should be able to propose multiple activities for the same time slot	Activity management	High
48	Problematic timeslots	Users should be able to see time slots that are problematic (when the minimum number of volunteers or children is not reached, or when there is an unbalanced ration between volunteers and children, etc) Using different colors to signal problematic and non-problematic timeslots	Activity management	High
49	Export agenda as XLS	Export an agenda with all activities in the group calendar for supporting discussion as XLS file (plugin)	Activity management	High
50	Calendar view	Users should be able to see calendar with: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - PERSONAL VIEW: the activities in which you are involved, and your children is involved in - GROUP VIEW: all the activities of that group 	Activity management Calendar	Medium
51	Toggle Calendar / List view	Users should be able to toggle view as calendar (month / week) or as a list (a list of timeslots)	Activity management	Medium

			Calendar	
53	Set constraints/ variables for slot confirmation	When creating an activity set the minimum number of children or volunteers required for each activity	Activity management	High
54	Who can propose an activity	Every group member can propose an activity and a group admin (<u>just one</u>) should agree	Activity management	Medium
55	Who can modify / confirm and close an activity	Only group administrators can modify or close or delete activities	Activity management	High
56	Activities detail	When you create an activity you define the title and the timeslots. Activity description, location, cost and image are optional.	Activity management	High
32	Evaluating an activity	When closed, activities can be evaluated by their members (e.g. with a questionnaire, a summary of the activity, a checklist)	Activity management	Medium
33	Sharing knowledge	Once finished, information on activities and groups can be shared within the community through the website	Activity management	Low

Table 5. Requirements related to creating and managing activities

The following wireframes visualize the interface features for proposing a new activity within the application.

CREATE A NEW ACTIVITY

 Tapping the FAB, the user can create a new activity to propose to the group members.

In order to create a new activity, the user is guided through three steps:

#1

i Informations

The user enters basic information on the activity such as the name, the location, the minimum number of participants and a color to recognize it in the calendar. Moreover, a description and a cost can be optionally added.

#2

📅 Dates

In the second step the user chooses the dates in which the activity will take place. One or more days can be selected by tapping on the calendar.

#3

🕒 Timeslots

The third step concerns the timeslots. The user can define the timetable of each day entering start and end time of the slot. Adding a new timeslot requires entering the time through a time picker.

Time slots can be added but can also be removed.

The user can choose to add different timeslots for each day.

EDIT AN ACTIVITY

Each timeslot can be modified individually and, therefore, have a title, a location, a minimum number of participants, a description and a cost different from the other slots.

The start time, the end time, the title, the number of participants and the cost changes are always visible without necessarily having to tap on the timeslot.

Before, but also after creating the activity, the user is free to go back to the previous steps and modify them.

6.2.4. Time and availability management and scheduling

The table below outlines the requirements related to time and availability management.

ID	Requirement	Description	Group	Priority
57	Timeslot information	Slots display the activity name, you can add a description, they have a counter for participation and a counter for children registered to that activity	Activity management	
58	Professionals and timeslots	If a professional is involved, he/she can be added in the time slot detail (by group administrators)	Activity management	High
59	Information on a timeslot	In a single time slot you can define the location and the description	Activity management	High
60	Apply changes to activity time for all the time slots	Users should be able to modify time for multiple time slots	Activity management	Medium
61	You can duplicate a time slot (for recurrent events)	Repeating a timeslots means repeating for a week/month/ same days	Activity management	Medium
63	Calendar in the homepage with commitment and fixed slots	A calendar showing all the activities in which I am involved (confirmed or open) or my children (confirmed or open) is displayed in the app homepage	Calendar	Low
64	Calendar with colors	The color represents time slots (days or weekly) colored if there is an activity for me / or my child(ren).	Calendar	Medium

Table 5. Requirements related to time and availability management and scheduling
The following wireframes described the functionalities for providing availabilities for the group activities.

SIGN UP FOR A TIMESLOT

The user can browse the timeslots in the activity page of a group. Users can search for slots viewing them by calendar activities or by daily timeslots.

The calendar shows the days in which one or more activities occur. Different colors represent different activities. By tapping on an activity, its details and timeslots can be modified.

Timeslots can have different background colors: white timeslots have not reached the minimum number of participants. Filled timeslots have instead enough participants and can be confirmed by the group administrator.

INTERACT WITH THE TIMESLOTS

The user can apply search filters to each slot.

Filter timeslots

- All timeslots ✓
- With enough participants
- Without enough participants
- My signed up

The parents and the child icons change color if the user or a member of the user family is signed up to the timeslot.

By tapping the information icon, the user can view and modify the timeslot details.

The activity icon shows the color of the timeslot. Tapping on it allows to see all the details and the timeslots of the related activity.

By tapping on a timeslot, the user can sign up him/herself and other family members to the activity.

The names of signed up members are always visible under the timeslot.

Tap on an already selected chip will unsubscribe the family member from the timeslot.

6.3. Interactive prototype and design specifications

At the following links we posted videos of the interactive prototype for presenting the main features of the Families_Share mobile application:

Interaction Video	Link	Description
Registration	https://drive.google.com/open?id=1W4YR0IVAnFkqkZiWrpcl6zsiQfzpe9qC	The video shows the landing page, with information on the project, and the sign up process
Login	https://drive.google.com/open?id=1Vmbpv2GxSqZbeiR22ZGubjF8VspkZkWB	Log-in process and homepage
See/Edit your profile	https://drive.google.com/open?id=1SM0fAthmNu6HfpfmSWR4qcXlbfmChAAk	The video shows how to see and edit the personal profile
Add/Edit children profile	https://drive.google.com/open?id=1z4CkTsk4VlwewGCD3Uog83qEEhafT-3b	The video shows how to add and edit information about the children
Search a group	https://drive.google.com/open?id=17bP1fj02BZNYVDLcM-zjwicLL624FYvH	How users can search for public groups and ask for invitation
Create a new group	https://drive.google.com/open?id=1hT55ioqe8v5z9AhjQ7hTOKusFLCgZgSF	The video shows the process of creating a new group
Receive a notification/message	https://drive.google.com/open?id=1HI4JjslUOyZp1g02XTg3M48VywDV0dn1	From the group page the user can read notifications and messages, and other information related to the group
View the calendar	https://drive.google.com/open?id=1eD6ly22kmZa854MDHr7IKHZh1CNGjTaJ	Users can change the view of their calendar
Create an activity	https://drive.google.com/open?id=1oo8hCXjPywuUm94BMFWi3--Hix2UDbOU	The video shows the guided process of creating a new activity and selecting time slots
Views activities and time slots	https://drive.google.com/open?id=1wSGfexoh6bNWhOHoTJLkAAXTGJ0e02ir	Users can visualize their calendar and a list of timeslots
Give availabilities	https://drive.google.com/open?id=1qaKRvMJby4JkKbhclDY9seQoMSY_rlgV	The video shows how users can indicate their availabilities or register their children to an activity

The interactive clickable prototypes (e.g. Figure 15) and the design specifications (e.g. Figure 16) can be accessed through these links:

Prototype features	Interactive Prototype	Design Specifications
Registration, user profile, creating and managing groups	https://xd.adobe.com/view/1be5a021-7f88-4dfc-4511-f90fd0fde495-6dd4/	https://xd.adobe.com/spec/fd22268c-60c7-4508-777a-e831b169dcdd-8b13/
Creating and managing activities, time and availability management and scheduling	https://xd.adobe.com/view/f28016f3-0d45-4cc3-5106-51a287603120-84b1/	https://xd.adobe.com/spec/3c57ad0a-4fda-495c-7c69-c29d59c596b4-4a66/

Figure 15. Visual representation of the interactive prototypes (created using Adobe XD)

Figure 16. A screen from the design specification generated in Adobe XD

Figure 17. Screenshot of the interactive prototype from Adobe XD for the activity scheduling task

Some visual mockups (Figure 18) were created to get a general idea of the final application and to better visualize how the application would appear on the device.

Figure 18. Mock-ups of the Families_Share application

7. Conclusions

This deliverable has provided:

- an analysis of digital application for childcare management and group time scheduling;
- the description of three usage scenarios and the result of a collaborative experience of the Cokido application;
- a list of requirements and a task flow map based on needs and experiences collected in the seven CityLabs;
- mockups, wireframes and interactive prototypes of the Families_Share platform detailing the features and the interaction that should be supported within the application.

This material provides a basis of communication and a source of clarification that will inform and guide the Families_Share platform and mobile services development.

References

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Johansson-Sköldberg, U., Woodilla, J., & Çetinkaya, M. (2013). Design thinking: past, present and possible futures. *Creativity and innovation management*, 22(2), 121-146.

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Annex

Annex 1. Scenarios presentation

Meet Lucia

Lucia is 44 years old and she has been married to Marco for 18 years. Together they have two children: Luca, 10 years old and Giada, 6 years old.

She has been working in a research centre in the northern Italy for 8 years now. This job for Lucia is fascinating and she loves it a lot.

Recently, she received a promotion that she desired for a long time. This implies more working hours though.

Life-work balance

Thus, Lucia struggles in balancing the job demands with those of her family.

Particularly, she has trouble when her children do not attend school but both her husband and she needs to work.

Carnival is arriving!

Carnival is approaching. Luca and Giada will be at home for the vacations but Lucia will have to work. Who will take care of her children?

She really does not have a solution.

Discover the platform

At the workplace, Lucia is at her desk, working on a project that has to be completed by the next day.

In that precise moment, she hears two colleagues discussing about an online platform for organising activities for their children when the school is closed. This platform is called Families_Share.

Get information

Lucia is very curious about this platform. She looked for it online and she accesses the Families_Share home page.

Lucia explores the page to collect more information on this platform.

By doing this, she discovers that the platform is based on the volunteering activity of some parents. The parents make available their own time and competences for covering specific periods according to their availability.

Sign up

Curious about the project, Lucia decides to sign up, by inserting her e-mail address and password.

Explore the platform

After signing up, she skims through the groups of parents who decided to organize and promote their activities in the website.

After reading some past activities, she notes that a particular group (Spark) is organizing an activity for covering the Thursday before Easter.

Lucia requests to join the group.

Join a group

By exploring the group, Lucia understands that it is composed of other 3 parents from her city.

Since its creation 5 activities have been carried out. Among them there are weekly laboratories (Painting, 3D Printing) and also visits at the local art museum.

Right now the group is organizing an activity for the Thursday before Easter and is looking for new members.

In order to define all details, a meeting has been called for the next day. Lucia decides to give a try.

Define the activities

At the meeting, all the group members are present, including the two group administrators and a moderator for conducting the discussion.

After Lucia introduces herself as the new member, the group defines together the details of the activity for covering the Thursday before Easter.

Among these decisions, a "robotic lab" will be organized from 9 to 12 in the morning while in the afternoon the children will be brought to celebrate Carnival from 14 to 17.

In agreement with all members, the group administrators assign different roles to support the process.

Provide children information

Now, on the platform, the page dedicated to the activity has been updated to reflect the decisions taken during the meeting.

Lucia's children, Luca e Giada, have been subscribed to the activity. However, the platform reminds that it is necessary to add some of their data.

Lucia fills in the requested information: name, date of birth and interests. Although there is also the possibility to add a picture, she decides against it by opting for an avatar instead.

Give your availability

Now that the basic information about Luca and Giada have been added, Lucia can express her availability as a parent to cover defined time slots of the day of Thursday before Easter.

She makes herself available for the lunch hour given that she will be busy both in the morning and in the afternoon.

Close the agenda

After a few days every time slots has been filled by the volunteers.

Thus, the group meets to check that everything is ready and to agree on the pending details.

At the end of the meeting all tasks have been accomplished and the activity has the green light!

Carry out the activity and have fun!

It is Thursday and Lucia is coming back to the office after having spent the lunch break from 12.30 to 14.00 with the Families_Share group.

In the morning she has accompanied her children to the "robotic lab". At lunch, Luca and Giada have told her about the activity with enthusiasm. Now they are looking forward to celebrating Carnival in the square.

Lucia is very happy with Families_Share. She has not only managed both her children and her job, but she is also meeting new parents and contributing to a successful and funny activity. The summer holidays are fast approaching and she has already some activities in her mind to propose, where she might have the chance to share her competences!

Annex 2. Cokido experience material

COKIDO – co-creation exercise

Dear consortium partner,

We kindly invite you to participate in an **internal test and co-creation exercise** around the COKIDO application with all consortium partners.

This exercise is specifically prepared for you by De Stuyveri and by IMEC, and should allow you to better understand the processes (both online and offline) and features of arranging childcare through co-playing with COKIDO. The exercise follows the journey that is stipulated in D1.1, and describes a user scenario for you to be completed. Of course, this is a fictive scenario but comes close to reality about how parents currently meet offline through COKIDO, how they form a group and arrange the activity, how they prepare the agenda, etc.

To complete the exercise, please execute the following steps by 17/7 (before you leave to Venice):

1. **Check in which community you belong.** There are two groups: the "Red Devils" and "Disney World".
2. **Check which role you have, and how many children.** There are four roles: (i) coordinator of the community, (ii) responsible person for the playing material, (iii) responsible person for the management of the location, (iv) co-playing parent. If you are assigned to be the coordinator of the community, then you will have more responsibilities on the COKIDO application than others.
3. **Execute the tasks in the scenario.** Go to the scenario of your corresponding group, and complete the tasks that are written in the last column. For registering on the application, you can check the document "CokidoApp_RegisterManual". To complete your actions on the application, it might be that some actions have to be completed by others first.

COKIDO – co-creation exercise

4. **Fill in the feedback form.** When you are finished with all the tasks (it might be that you are reliant on the action of others, before you can complete yours), please complete the feedback form and send it back to nie@destuyveri.be, info@destuyveri.be and carina.veeckman@imec.be.

Useful documents:

- How to register on the COKIDO application (as some screens are still in Dutch): <http://bit.ly/2JbvtKd>
- Planning group I "Red Devils": <http://bit.ly/2XKX03r>
- Planning group II "Disney World": <http://bit.ly/2JbvtKd>

Everything is also available on the team drive > De Stuyveri > COKIDO platform scenario

COKIDO – co-creation exercise

GROUP 1: "Red Devils"

No.	Participant/parent	Children	Role
1	Chiara Lomardi	Child 1: "Toby" – 3 years old Child 2: "Micky" – 5 years old	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Coordinator of the community creating the group online Creating the childcare weeks online Responsible for financial management Responsible for checking filled in slots for the agenda, and closing the agenda Responsible for adding "babysitters" or "family" for open slots Co-playing parent
2	Massimo Zancanaro	Child 1: "Laurent" – 4 years old	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Responsible for the playing material Co-playing parent
3	Agostino Cortesi	Child 1: "Dino" – 6 years old Child 2: "Eden" – 7 years old Child 3: "Tim" – 10 years old	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Responsible for the management of the location Co-playing parent
4	Carina Veeckman	Child 1: "Manuela" – 7 years old	Co-playing parent
5	Maria Sanguliano	Child 1: "Kevin" – 7 years old	Co-playing parent
6	Nick Kinds	Child 1: "Thomas" – 6 years old	Co-playing parent
7	Apostolos Vontas	Child 1: "Lukas" – 7 years old	Co-playing parent
8	Leif Coltenen	Child 1: "Hannes" – 8 years old	Co-playing parent
9	Khadja Ouchouak	Child 1: "Hassan" – 10 years old	Co-playing parent

COKIDO – co-creation exercise

GROUP 2: "Disney World"

No.	Participant/parent	Children	Role
1	Manolis Panagos	Child 1: "Anna" – 3 years old Child 2: "Ella" – 5 years old	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Coordinator of the community creating the group online Creating the childcare weeks online Responsible for financial management Responsible for checking filled in slots for the agenda, and closing the agenda Responsible for adding "babysitters" or "family" for open slots Co-playing parent
2	Karina Czaio	Child 1: "Tinker bell" – 4 years old	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Responsible for the playing material Co-playing parent
3	Popi Sourmaidou	Child 1: "Dimitri" – 6 years old Child 2: "Sofia" – 7 years old Child 3: "Philo" – 10 years old	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Responsible for the management of the location Co-playing parent
4	Maria Ceccon	Child 1: "Anna" – 7 years old	Co-playing parent
5	Elise Charles	Child 1: "Wilma" – 7 years old	Co-playing parent
6	Miriam Chatzomalis	Child 1: "Tigger" – 5 years old	Co-playing parent
7	Maria Schulte	Child 1: "Cinderella" – 7 years old Child 2: "Bella" – 8 years old	Co-playing parent
8	Annelies Maertens	Child 1: "Jafar" – 8 years old	Co-playing parent
9	Mattia Casola	Child 1: "Simba" – 10 years old	Co-playing parent

COKIDO – co-creation exercise

User scenario
GROUP I: "RED DEVILS"

COKIDO – co-creation exercise

USER JOURNEY COKIDO: Providing flexible child care during holidays periods for the RED DEVILS COMMUNITY

CONSIDER THE OPPORTUNITY	DISCOVER THE COMMUNITY	DISCOVER THE NEEDS	ACTING ON COKIDO
A community manager configures the community	In May 2018, Massimo got familiar with the COKIDO application when he saw an article about it in a magazine, and started to learn more about it. He visited the contact details and made an appointment with the community manager of the COKIDO application, named Roberto. During their first appointment, Roberto explained all the phases of self-organizing childcare and helped Massimo with downloading and registering on the application. Roberto showed him the main features for creating and managing groups. After this contact, he felt reassured that he could convince other parents to join. He also received some brochures from the community manager to distribute to interested parents.	At the end of May, after the football game of his son Midy, Massimo talks to other parents, being Chiara and Agostino, at the local football club in their village. He hears that they are looking for childcare during the summer period, as summer camps are becoming quite expensive. Massimo explains them the idea of COKIDO and tells that when he will return back home from the football club, he will send a website link to Chiara and Agostino to have a look at the COKIDO application. After downloading and registering on the application, Chiara and Agostino like the idea, and agree to form a core group with Massimo to self-organize childcare during the summer holidays.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Chiara and Agostino register on the COKIDO application, and fill in the profile details Massimo creates the "Red Devils" group Chiara and Agostino become a member of the "Red Devils" group
Parent has a need	Discovers families share	Discovers the need	ACTING ON COKIDO
Download application and register			

<p>To form a group, they need to look for other parents, as the group should consist of minimum 10 parents. Massimo, Chiara, and Agnese decide that after the next football game of their sons, they will talk to other parents and hand them over a brochure from the COXIDO application. For now, the three of them form the core group and have downloaded the application, and filled in all profile details: the parent's profile, and the child profiles. Further, as group coordinator, Massimo created the group "Red Devil" in the application of which Chiara and Agnese are the first members. Chiara and Agnese could find the "red devil" group through the search function, and by clicking "participate in this group".</p>		
GROUP MEMBERSHIP	GROUP MEMBERSHIP	ACTIONS ON COXIDO
<p>Join a group</p> <p>Create a group</p> <p>Receive an invitation to join a group</p>	<p>After the next football game in June, Chiara, Massimo and Agnese sit in Carina, Maria, Neli, Apostolos, Efe and Khadija in the safe area of the club about their idea to self-arrange child care with a group of parents in the summer period. They all like the idea, and agree to participate in the group "Red Devil" to self-arrange child care.</p> <p>When back home, Massimo sends an invitation to Carina, Maria, Neli, Apostolos, Efe and Khadija to join the "red devil" group on the COXIDO application. For doing this, Massimo goes to the menu "members", and clicks "invite persons", and enters their email addresses. After entering all email addresses, Massimo has an overview of who has already accepted the invitation (or not).</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Massimo invites Carina, Maria, Neli, Apostolos, Efe and Khadija via their email to join the "red devil" group. Carina, Maria, Neli, Apostolos, Efe and Khadija accept the invitation of Massimo and register on the COXIDO application. Carina, Maria, Neli, Apostolos, Efe and Khadija complete the profile details.

GROUP LIFE OFFICE	GROUP LIFE OFFICE	ACTIONS ON COXIDO
<p>First members meet offline</p> <p>Invite other participants</p> <p>Negotiate agreements</p> <p>Enforce an activity</p>	<p>Carina, Maria, Neli, Apostolos, Efe and Khadija open their mailbox (check spam!) and see that they have received an invitation from Massimo for the group "Red Devil". They accept the invite and download and register on the COXIDO application. They fill in all the profile details about themselves and their children. They see in the application that there are now members of the group "Red Devil".</p> <p>Massimo, as group coordinator, also sets up a Whatsapp group for the "red devil" by entering all the phone numbers that she found online in the profiles on COXIDO (this is better and does not need to happen right now). He sends the group for an offline invitation to meet up and to settle all the arrangements, the facts "first online meet up, now Wednesday 13/7/2018 at 14 o'clock, at the cafeteria to discuss the possibilities for arranging child care in summer". The parents all affirm that they will come.</p> <p>During the meeting they discuss for which periods in July and August they have the most pressing needs to self-arrange child care, they also exchange their availabilities: when are the parents able to co-play, and at which moments should child care be provided. As such, the first steps of the planning are made offline, whereby it is decided which weeks in July and August will be chosen for arranging child care, and who as a parent can be available. Since they are with a group of new parents, it is also still necessary that they look for a fourth</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> All have a look to the planning that was made offline during 13/7/2018. http://bit.ly/2ZDXXK1 Agnese posts a message on the dashboard of the group about the location: e.g. Primary school Saint Nicholas, Saint-Nicholas street 5, Gent. Chiara posts a message on the dashboard about the playing material.

<p>person. Massimo will be responsible for adding this sixth person into the system, this can be another family from the football club, or a grandparent, or a babysitter who can cover the needs on a specific day.</p> <p>Agnese, who is responsible for the management of the location, questions the parents which location they find the most suitable to arrange the children's activities. From Roberto, the community manager of COXIDO, they received some recommendations of places nearby which are suitable, and also a list of guidelines of requirements for suitable locations. The group decides that they will ask the primary school, where most of the children go, for using their classrooms during the summer period. When Agnese will reach an agreement with them, he will write a message on the dashboard in the COXIDO application with the specific about the location, such as "Primary school Saint Nicholas, Saint-Nicholas street 5, Gent". Agnese will post this information on the dashboard.</p> <p>Chiara, who is responsible for the playing material, also questions the parents if they could bring along one toy per child for the children's activities, or if they know someone who can borrow or donate playing material. After the meet-up, Chiara also posts a message on the dashboard regarding the playing material, so that parents do not forget about their commitment.</p>		
GROUP COORDINATION & PARTICIPATION MANAGEMENT	GROUP COORDINATION & PARTICIPATION MANAGEMENT	ACTIONS ON COXIDO
<p>Insert availability as volunteer</p> <p>Insert participation of number of children</p>	<p>How the planning is made. Massimo enters the periods for August, from 20/8 to 24/8 with time slots 08:00 - 12:00 and 12:00 - 17:00. He defines all the group conditions: start and end time (time slots) & maximum amount of children per parent for one day (max. 4 children / parent).</p> <p>Massimo creates the period in the agenda "20/8 to 24/8 and fills in all the settings: start and end slots, and maximum amount of children per parent."</p> <p>Massimo enters his availability and needed child care days for his children.</p> <p>Agnese, Chiara, Carina, Maria, Neli, Apostolos, Efe and Khadija go back online to the COXIDO application and enter their availability as co-playing parent, and insert the participation of their children for the specific needed days. For entering this information, please consult excel sheet http://bit.ly/2ZDXXK1.</p> <p>The planning is now confirmed for the parents and the children, with the exception of one specific day for which a parent is lacking. Therefore, Massimo posts a message on the dashboard to ask the group if someone can help for that specific day. Marla replies that her sister can cover that day, and that her</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> All everyone clicks on the period "20/8 to 24/8" to participate. All everyone enters his availability as co-playing parent, and for which days child care is needed. Check the "Google excel sheet" http://bit.ly/2ZDXXK1. Massimo posts a message on the dashboard to ask

GROUP COORDINATION & PARTICIPATION MANAGEMENT	GROUP COORDINATION & PARTICIPATION MANAGEMENT	ACTIONS ON COXIDO
<p>Insert availability as volunteer</p> <p>Insert participation of number of children</p>	<p>spot with all the necessary health information and contact information of the other parents, in case of an emergency.</p> <p>Massimo keeps track of the costs that are made per day, and enters this into the system. For instance, on the first day some ice creams were bought for the children, for 20 euros.</p> <p>The week is smoothly organized, and Maria and Agnese have also organized a walk to the forest with water games on their co-playing day. They post some pictures about the activities on the dashboard in the group (but only from children whose parents agreed with it).</p> <p>The COXIDO week is finished, and all parents and children start to prepare themselves again for the start of new school term in September.</p> <p>Before that, Massimo would like to know how everyone experienced the self-arranged child care in August. He invites Chiara and Agnese to come over to her place, with also Carina, Apostolos and Efe and make some notes about what went good, and what could be improved for the next time.</p> <p>Afterwards, they transfer these notes to Roberto of COXIDO.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> All everyone clicks on the period "20/8 to 24/8" to participate. All everyone enters his availability as co-playing parent, and for which days child care is needed. Check the "Google excel sheet" http://bit.ly/2ZDXXK1. Massimo posts a message on the dashboard to ask

<p>name and email address is: Sofia, suffa@stefanoroberto.com. Massimo enters these final details into the agenda.</p> <p>for an extra co-playing parent or caregiver for 24/8.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Maria replies on the dashboard that her sister can help. Massimo enters the details into the system of Maria's sister, underneath the field "babysitter". 		
OFFLINE PICK-UP	OFFLINE PICK-UP	ACTIONS ON COXIDO
<p>Members meet offline</p> <p>Close the agenda</p>	<p>Close to the actual group activity in August. Massimo hosts a barbecue party with a jumping castle for the children in his garden. All parents from the "red devil" group are invited, as well as Roberto from COXIDO. During this activity, the children and parents who are not yet familiar with each other can make acquaintance. Massimo also questions the parents one more time to know if they are sure about the chosen time slots, and if he is able to close the agenda.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Massimo closes the agenda.
RUN ACTIVITY	RUN ACTIVITY	ACTIONS ON COXIDO
<p>Access information about children</p> <p>Update parents</p>	<p>The children's week starts and the first day of the week is done by Maria, Agnese and Neli. The children of Massimo, Chiara and Apostolos are also present that day. The others did not need childcare for this specific day.</p> <p>Agnese made sure that the base were available for them, and also made sure that the child info sheets were available on the</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Massimo enters the costs from 20/8 to 24/8. Maria and Agnese posts some pictures on the dashboard from 21/8.

EVALUATE	EVALUATE	ACTIONS ON COXIDO
<p>Evaluate the activity/group</p> <p>Change group agreement/improve group management</p>	<p>Before that, Massimo would like to know how everyone experienced the self-arranged child care in August. He invites Chiara and Agnese to come over to her place, with also Carina, Apostolos and Efe and make some notes about what went good, and what could be improved for the next time.</p> <p>Afterwards, they transfer these notes to Roberto of COXIDO.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> All everyone clicks on the period "20/8 to 24/8" to participate. All everyone enters his availability as co-playing parent, and for which days child care is needed. Check the "Google excel sheet" http://bit.ly/2ZDXXK1. Massimo posts a message on the dashboard to ask

User scenario
GROUP II: "DISNEY WORLD"

CONFIGURE THE COMMUNITY	CONFIGURE THE COMMUNITY	ACTIONS ON COXIDO
<p>A community manager configures the community</p>	<p>In May 2018, Maria got familiar with the COXIDO application when she saw an article about it in a magazine, and wanted to learn more about it. She wrote down the contact details and made an appointment with the community manager of the COXIDO application, named Walt. During their first appointment, Walt explained all the phases of self-arranging childcare, and helped Maria with downloading and registering on the application. Walt showed her the main features for creating and managing groups. After this contact, she felt reassured that she could convince other parents to join. She also received some brochures from the community manager to distribute to interested parents.</p>	<p>Maria registers on the COXIDO application, and fills in the profile details.</p>
DISCOVER	DISCOVER	ACTIONS ON COXIDO
<p>Parent has a need</p> <p>Discovers families share</p> <p>Downloads application and register</p>	<p>At the end of May, when Maria comes to pick up her daughter Ana and Ella at the school gate, she talks with some other parents, being Karolina and Papi, about the arrangement of child care during summer. The mothers say that they are looking for alternative childcare during the summer period, as summer camps are becoming quite expensive. Maria explains them the idea of COXIDO and tells that when she will return back home, she will send a website link to Karolina and Papi to have a look at the COXIDO application. After downloading and registering on the application, Karolina and Papi like the idea, and agree to</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Karolina and Papi register on the COXIDO application, and fill in the profile details. Maria creates the "Red Devil" group. Karolina and Papi become a member of the "Disney World" group.

COVIDO - co-creation exercise

		form a core group with Marie to self-arrange childcare during the summer holidays. To form a group, they need to look for other parents, as the group should consist of minimum 10 parents. Marie, Karolina and Papi decide that during parents' council at school, they will talk to other parents and hand them over a brochure from the COVIDO application. For now, the three of them form the core group and have downloaded the application, and filled in all profile details: the parent's profile, and the child profiles. Further, as group coordinator, Marie created the group 'Disney world' in the application of which Karolina and Papi are the first members. Karolina and Papi could find the 'Disney world' group through the search function, and by clicking 'participate in this group'.	
GROUP MISSIONS	GROUP DEVELOPMENT	ACTIONS ON COVIDO	
Join a group	Create a group	Receive an invitation to join a group	<p>Marie meets Marie, Eline, Mpmapi, Manolis, Annelies and Mattia via their email to join the 'Disney world' group.</p> <p>Marie, Eline, Mpmapi, Manolis, Annelies and Mattia accept the invitation of Marie and register on the COVIDO application.</p> <p>Marie, Eline, Mpmapi, Manolis, Annelies, and</p>

COVIDO - co-creation exercise

		accepted the invitation (or not). Marie, Eline, Mpmapi, Manolis, Annelies and Mattia open their mailboxes and see that they have received an invitation from Marie for the group 'Disney world'. They accept the invite and download and register on the COVIDO application. They fill in all the profile details about themselves and their children. They see in the application that there are members of the group 'Disney world'.	Mattia complete the profile details
GROUP LIFE OFFLINE	GROUP LIFE OFFLINE	ACTIONS ON COVIDO	
First members meet offline	Invite other participants	Negotiate agreements	<p>Marie, as group coordinator, also sets up a Whatsapp group for the 'Disney world' group by entering all the phone numbers that she found online in the profiles on COVIDO (this is done and does not need to happen right now). She texts the group for an offline invitation to meet up and to settle all the arrangements. She texts 'first online meet up: now Wednesday 15/7/2018 at 14 o'clock, at the tavern close to the school to discuss the possibilities for arranging child care in summer'. The parents all agree that they will come.</p> <p>During the meeting they discuss for which periods in July and August they have the most pressing needs to self-arrange child care, they also exchange their availabilities, when are the parents able to co-play, and at which moments should child care be provided. As such, the first steps of the planning are made offline, whereby it is decided which weeks in July and August will be chosen for arranging child care, and who a parent can be available. Since they go with a group of</p>

COVIDO - co-creation exercise

		five parents. It is also still necessary that they look for a tenth person. Marie will be responsible for adding the tenth person into the system, this can be other parents from the school, a grandparent, or a babysitter who can cover the needs on a specific day.	
GROUP COORDINATION & PARTICIPATION MANAGEMENT	GROUP COORDINATION & PARTICIPATION MANAGEMENT	ACTIONS ON COVIDO	
Invite	Invite other participants	Negotiate agreements	<p>Karolina, who is responsible for the management of the location, questions the parents which location they find the most suitable to arrange the childcare activities. From Walt, the community manager of COVIDO, they received some recommendations of places nearby which are suitable, and also sent a list of guidelines of requirements for suitable locations. The group decides that they will ask the primary school, where all children go, for using their classrooms during the summer period. When Karolina will reach an agreement with them, she will write a message on the dashboard in the COVIDO application with the specifics about the location, such as: 'Primary school Saint Jacobs, Saint-Jacobs street 5, Gent'. Karolina will post this information on the dashboard.</p> <p>Papi, who is responsible for the playing material, also questions the parents if they could bring along one toy per child for the childcare activities, or if they know someone who can borrow or donate playing material. After the meeting, Papi also posts a message on the dashboard regarding the playing material, so that parents do not forget about their commitment.</p>

COVIDO - co-creation exercise

		How the planning is made. Marie enters the periods for August, from 20/08 to 24/08 with time slots 09:00 - 12:30 and 13:30 - 17:00. She defines all the group conditions: start and end time (time slots), maximum amount of children per parent for each day (max. 6 children / parent).	Mattia creates the period in the agenda '20/8 to 24/8' and fills in all the settings: start and end slots, and maximum amount of children per parent.
GROUP COORDINATION & PARTICIPATION MANAGEMENT	GROUP COORDINATION & PARTICIPATION MANAGEMENT	ACTIONS ON COVIDO	
Insert	Insert participation of number of children	Insert participation of number of children	<p>Karolina, Papi, Marie, Eline, Mpmapi, Manolis, Annelies and Mattia go back online to the COVIDO application and enter their availability as a co-playing parent, and insert the participation of their children for the specific needed days. For entering this information, please consult excel sheet.</p> <p>The planning is now confirmed for the parents and the children, with the exception of one specific day for which a parent is lacking. Therefore, Marie posts a message on the dashboard to ask the group if someone can help for that specific day. Manolis replies that his sister can cover that day, and that her name and email address is Lisa.</p>

COVIDO - co-creation exercise

		an extra co-playing parent or caregiver for 24/8.	
OFFLINE CHECK-OFF	OFFLINE CHECK-OFF	ACTIONS ON COVIDO	
Members meet offline	Close the agenda	Close to the actual group activity in August. Marie hosts a barbecue party with a jumping castle for the children in her garden. All parents from the 'Disney world' group are invited, as well as Walt from COVIDO. During this activity, the children and parents, who are not yet familiar with each other, can make acquaintance. Marie also questions the parents one more time to know if there are sure about the chosen time slots, and if she is able to close the agenda.	<p>Marie closes the agenda</p>
FOR ACTIVITY	FOR ACTIVITY	ACTIONS ON COVIDO	
Access information about children	Update parents	Update parents	<p>Marie enters the costs from 20/8-20 euros</p> <p>Manolis and Mattia post some pictures on the dashboard from 21/8</p>

COVIDO - co-creation exercise

		on the spot with all the necessary health information and contact information of the other parents, in case of an emergency.	
EVALUATE	EVALUATE	ACTIONS ON COVIDO	
Evaluate the activity/group	Change group agreement/improve group management	The COVIDO week is finished, and all parents and children start to prepare themselves again for the start of next school semester in September.	<p>Marie keeps track of the costs that are made per day, and enters this into the system. For instance, on the first day some ice creams were bought for the children, for 20 euros.</p> <p>The week is smoothly organized, and Marie and Manolis have also organized a walk to the forest with water games on their co-playing day. They post some pictures about the activities on the dashboard in the group (but only from children whose parents agreed with it).</p> <p>Before that, Marie would like to know how everyone experienced the self-arranged child care in August. She invites Karolina and Papi to come over to her place, with also Annelies, Mattia and Eline and make some notes about what went good, and what could be improved for the next time. Afterwards, they transfer their notes to Walt of COVIDO.</p>

FEEDBACK FORM

Please write down your feedback here, and send it to parkevoel@families.be and info@families.be

1. My name:					
2A. To what extent do you think the user journey with scenario was well explained for you?	Not clear at all	Unclear	Neither unclear, nor clear	Clear	Very clear
2B. Can you please provide some explanation for your provided answer above? <i>(e.g. should extra steps be added to the user journey, was it difficult to follow for you, did you know what to do etc.)</i>					
What do you think is currently working well on the COVIDO application?					
What do you think is currently not working so well on the COVIDO application?					

COVIDO - co-creation exercise

To what extent do you think that the current system is usable for the 'flexible' scenario of organizing child care in your city/lab?	
Please provide any other feedback about the COVIDO application in the text box.	

Annex 3. Full requirement list

Legend:

ID: Identification number

Requirement: Title of the requirement

Description: Detailed requirement description

Notes: Notes or criticalities associated with the requirements

Category: Requirement category

Priority: Requirement order of importance (from high to low)

Prototype version: Whether the requirement is addressed in the prototype presented in this deliverable (v1) or if it will be addressed in the second release (v2)

ID	Requirement	Description	Notes	Category	Priority	Prototype version
1	Website for each community	Each community has a website as companion of the app (each CityLab can have more than one community) Perhaps we could use second level domains for these (e.g. trento.families-share.eu).		Website	High	v1
2	Website shows the list of groups for that community (as in Cokido)	We can create an endpoint within the app that returns information about public groups. So the website could be totally static, apart from the content shown from that endpoint. That way one could browse some public groups and perhaps see photos, just like in Cokido. If they click on the group however, they will need to download the app and register.		Website	Low	v1
3	The app has different instances	Each community will have its app to download from the Google Play Store (android first and then iOS later on)		General	High	v1
4	App design is mobile first	The interface will be designed mainly for mobile phones but it can be access also from the web (for iOS and web users)		General	High	v1
5	Search group	Users can search for groups from the web page or from the mobile app		Search	High	v1
6	Search users	New users should be able to search for other users and ask them to join her/his group Should it be optional?	Sharing phone number or other contact to the public	Search	Low	v2
7	User name visibility	User should be able to decide if their name should be searchable (visible / not visible)	Depend on user search	User profile Privacy	High	v1
8	User search visibility	Some users could decide to be invisible to the community. If they are not visible, to add them to a group or as a parent you should input the email or telephone number		User profile Privacy	High	v1
9	Cancel profile	Users should be able to cancel all their information		User profile	High	v1

				Privacy		
10	Suspend profile	Users should be able to suspend their profile		User profile Privacy	Medium	v2
11	Export all information	Users should be able to export all their data stored in the platform (as JSON)		User profile Privacy	High	v1
12	Integrate children information within the platform	Children information should be provided within the app (not in a printed form) Data should be encrypted		Children info Privacy	High	v1
13	Showing children basic information + special needs	Children basic information such as name, age and gender should be visible to the other members of the group (when organizing an activity) If there is any special needs, a symbol can be placed next to the children name Integrate child card inside the app. So that we can search e.g. based on the age of the participants of the group. Age and gender are most important info too. Perhaps also add information about possible health issues (call it "special needs").		Children info	Medium	v1
14	Managing who can view your full children information	When users provide their children information they should be notified and accept that these information can be shared with other members of the group. Users should be able to decide who can see this info. [Information sharing option]	To be refined in WP2	Children info Privacy	High	v2
15	Export children information	Users should be able to export in a PDF file the children information of the activity they are involved		Children info Privacy	High	v1
16	Privacy consent at the registration	When users register in the platform, the platform should make sure that consent is "informed consent" and provide necessary privacy notice and other information at the time user consent is required. The registration process stops if user do not provide the consent		Log-in / Registration Privacy	High	v1
17	Parents can add other users as parents	Parents have different profile and their share the same children profile A parent can be added as co-parent / guardian / family member	! terms: parents / guardian / (family?)	Children info User profile	Medium	v1

18	User hierarchy	Community manager <- Group administrator <- User (parents / professionals) <- External [i.e. person not registered in the platform] This means that the community manager is inherently a Group administrator for all groups The Professional is a user role that has certain permissions.		User categories	High	v1
19	New member notification	When a new member enter a group all other members are notified	Privacy implications	Notification	Medium	v1
20	New member acceptance rule	Two options are provided: Strict: all members (who are also group administrators) they have to agree to the new member Flexible: at least one group administrator agrees	Decided at the community level (the default)	Group management Community management	High	???
21	Single sign on	This is an optional feature. We will start with registering for a local account functionality and perhaps integrate that in the future.		Log-in / Registration	Low	v1
22	Community default options	Options when you create a community: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New members are automatically administrator OR not • Approval for new members: Do all group administrators need to agree? Or just one is fine? (i.e. AND or OR). [see #20] Group can change this option or not		Community management	Medium	???
23	Community access option	The community can be open or not		Community management	Medium	v1
24	Group settings when creating a group	A group can be visible or not visible: that is a group can be searchable or not. If it is visible, an external user can contact the group administrator for joining the group		Group management Privacy	Medium	v1
25	Join a group with an invite	All groups are invite-only. Some are visible and some are not. If it is not visible you have to receive an invite by the group administrator to join in. If the group is visible, you can contact the group administrator to receive an invite.		Group management	High	v1
26	Type of notifications	Members and group administrators should receive notifications. System event notifications e.g: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - "a new user entered the group" - "a new activity has been created" - "the agenda for a specific activity was closed" The notification can be sent in the phone or by email		Notifications	High	v1
27	Phone notifications	Phone notifications are enabled		Notifications	Medium	v2

28	Professional users	<p>Professionals can be invited by group administrators. They are users and can access information related to the activity in which they are involved</p> <p>OR we can keep as it is in Cokido (information provided in the activity by the group administrator)</p>	<p>This requirement should be discussed with other partners</p> <p>To be refined in WP2</p>	User categories	Medium	v2
29	Assign group roles	<p>Group administrators can assign different roles to the members (e.g. location manager, financial manager, ...)</p> <p>For now it is just a text field</p> <p>Possibly implements checklists (one for a "group administrator") for supporting in managing group roles</p>	We can add it as text in the description of the group	User categories	Low	v2
30	Types of activities	<p>The interface should support activities that have two characteristics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Recurrent vs One-time - Flexible vs Fixed <p>User should not categorize the type of activity, this can be automatically inferred by the system</p>		Activity management	High	v1
31	Promote groups and activity	We should provide indications or material for supporting the promotion of groups or activities (flyer, social media material, etc)		<p>Group management</p> <p>Activity management</p>	Low	v1
32	Evaluating an activity	When closed, activities can be evaluated by their members (e.g. with a questionnaire, a summary of the activity, a checklist)		Activity management	Medium	v2
33	Sharing knowledge	Once finished, information on activities and groups can be shared within the community through the website		Activity management	Low	v2
34	Starting page / Homepage for new users	<p>Information displayed to the users when they access the platform:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Login Registration form - Info on Families_Shares project - Info on active groups 		Interface	Medium	v1
35	Starting page / Homepage for registered users	<p>Information displayed to the registered users when they enter the application:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Calendar - Joined groups - Notifications 		Interface	Medium	v1
36	Provide checklists	Provide users with checklists for supporting some activities (WhatsApp group creation, financial rules, etc.)		Interface	High	v1
37	Log-in with email	Allows log-in with email address	This requirement should be discussed with other partners	Log-in / Registration	High	v1

			To be refined in WP2			
38	Log-in with SMS	Allows log-in with SMS (not only with an email)	This requirement should be discussed with other partners This log-in option might require a paid service To be refined in WP2	Log-in / Registration	Medium	v2
39	Support communication within and outside the app	Communication can be supported within the app (announcements / message) or outside (WhatsApp/Telegram/facebook). This can be decided by the community manager.	The type of communication should be decided at the community level	Communication Community management	Medium	v1
40	Announcements (a.k.a. Messaging) feature	Kept as they are in Cokido (basic) but call them Announcements and have it for informing group members This can include also info for support the group to manage a whatsapp / telegram group Users should be able to post message and give replies	To be refined in WP2	Communication	High	v1
41	Edit announcements / replies	You can edit announcements or replies (created by you)		Communication	Medium	v1
42	Deleting announcements / replies	You can delete announcements or replies (created by you)		Communication	Medium	v1
43	“Twitter” style notification	Receive only one notification with information on the number of #	Depend on phone notifications	Communication	Low	v2
44	Images in the announcements	Announcements can include an image		Communication	Medium	v1
45	Activities are mapped in a collection of timeslots	When you create an activity you set a time range (and this can be edited) and define time slots		Activity management	High	v1
46	Timeslots have counters	Users should be able to mark their availabilities and their need for each timeslot Counters can represent volunteer availabilities AND needs (children)		Activity management	High	v1
47	Propose different activities	Users should be able to propose multiple activities for the same time slot	Requirement from Venice	Activity management	High	v1

48	Problematic timeslots	Users should be able to see time slots that are problematic (when the minimum number of volunteers or children is not reached, or when there is an unbalanced ration between volunteers and children, etc) Using different colors to signal problematic and non-problematic timeslots	Specify what problematic means (min/max # of children, min # of volunteers)	Activity management	High	v1
49	Export agenda as XLS	Export an agenda with all activities in the group calendar for supporting discussion as XLS file (plugin)	Requirement from Venice	Activity management	High	v1
50	Calendar view	Users should be able to see calendar with: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - PERSONAL VIEW: the activities in which you are involved, and your children is involved in - GROUP VIEW: all the activities of that group 		Activity management Calendar	Medium	v1
51	Toggle Calendar / List view	Users should be able to toggle view as calendar (month / week) or as a list (a list of timeslots)		Activity management Calendar	Medium	v1
52	Optimal solution	The application proposes optimal solution after collecting votes		Activity management	Low	v2
53	Set constraints/ variables for slot confirmation	When creating an activity set the minimum number of children or volunteers required for each activity		Activity management	High	v1
54	Who can propose an activity	Every group member can propose an activity and a group admin (<u>just one</u>) should agree	This could be changed in future versions	Activity management	Medium	v1
55	Who can modify / confirm and close an activity	Only group administrators can modify or close or delete activities	This could be changed in future versions	Activity management	High	v1
56	Activities detail	When you create an activity you define the title and the timeslots. Activity description, location, cost and image are optional.		Activity management	High	v1
57	Timeslot information	Slots display the activity name, you can add a description, they have a counter for participation and a counter for children registered to that activity		Activity management	High	v1
58	Professionals and timeslots	If a professional is involved, he/she can be added in the time slot detail (by group administrators)	See 28	Activity management	High	v1
59	Information on a timeslot	In a single time slot you can define the location and the description		Activity management	High	v1
60	Apply changes to activity time for all the time slots	Users should be able to modify time for multiple time slots		Activity management	Medium	v1

61	You can duplicate a time slot (for recurrent events)	Repeating a timeslots means repeating for a week/month/ same days	Define duplication options	Activity management	Medium	v1
62	Export in your calendar	Export an activity calendar (once it is fixed) to your digital calendar		Calendar	Low	v2
63	Calendar in the homepage with commitment and fixed slots	A calendar showing all the activities in which I am involved (confirmed or open) or my children (confirmed or open) is displayed in the app homepage		Calendar	Low	v1
64	Calendar with colors	The color represents time slots (days or weekly) colored if there is an activity for me / or my child(ren).		Calendar	Medium	v1

Annex 4. Wireframes and material used in the design sprint workshop

COKIDO co-design workshop material

User profile (overview) 1/21

User profile (creation) 2/21

Add children profile 3/21

Group member info 10/21

Invite members 12/21

Periods (blank) 16/21

Invite f(r)amily member 4/21

Starting page 5/21

Create new periods 15/21

Group members overview 11/21

Periods (with info)

Create new period (options)

Period detail

Side bar

Create new group

Search groups

Settings (overview)

Settings (variables)

Edit group info

Request invitation

Group messages

Annex 5. Color palette proposals and survey results

Color Scheme #1

Color Scheme #2

Color Scheme #3

Please rank your preferences

Preference scores collected among the consortium partners through the online survey

Annex 6. Mobile application wireframes

Homepage and log-in

Registration and sign-up

Sign up

Do you already have an account? [Log in](#)

Name

Phone Number (optional)

Email

Password

Confirm password

My profile appears in search results

I accept the Terms of Use and the Policy in regards to the treatment and use of my data.

CONFIRM

Sign up 2

Do you already have an account? [Log in](#)

Name
Lucia Bianchi

Phone Number (optional)

Email

Password

Confirm password

My profile appears in search results

I accept the Terms of Use and the Policy in regards to the treatment and use of my data.

CONFIRM

Sign up 3

Do you already have an account? [Log in](#)

Name
Lucia Bianchi

Phone number
+48 12345678

Label
Mobile

Email

Password

Confirm password

My profile appears in search results

I accept the Terms of Use and the Policy in regards to the treatment and use of my data.

CONFIRM

Sign up 4

Do you already have an account? [Log in](#)

Name
Lucia Bianchi

Phone number
+48 12345678

Label
Mobile

Email
lucia.bianchi@email.com

Password

Confirm password

My profile appears in search results

I accept the Terms of Use and the Policy in regards to the treatment and use of my data.

CONFIRM

Sign up 5

Do you already have an account? [Log in](#)

Name
Lucia Bianchi

Phone number
+48 12345678

Label
Mobile

Email
lucia.bianchi@email.com

Password
.....

Confirm password
.....

My profile appears in search results

I accept the Terms of Use and the Policy in regards to the treatment and use of my data.

CONFIRM

Sign up 6

Do you already have an account? [Log in](#)

Name
Lucia Bianchi

Phone number
+48 12345678

Label
Mobile

Email
lucia.bianchi@email.com

Password
.....

Confirm password
.....

My profile appears in search results

I accept the Terms of Use and the Policy in regards to the treatment and use of my data.

CONFIRM

User profile

The 'User profile' section displays five mobile app screens:

- User profile:** Shows the profile for Lucia Bianchi with contact details: +48 123 456 78 (Mobile), Church Street 45 (Address), and lucia.bianchi@email.com (Personal).
- User profile 2:** Shows Lucia Bianchi's profile with a child listed: Giada, 6 years old (Girl).
- User profile 3:** Shows Lucia Bianchi's profile with a list of family members: Aaron Jones, Amelia Kendrick, Anna D. Bennett, and Ben Kowalski.
- Modified profile:** Shows Lucia Bianchi's profile with updated contact details: +48 123 456 78 (Mobile), Church Street 45, Trento, Italy (Address), and lucia.bianchi@email.com (Personal).
- Child added to a...:** Shows Lucia Bianchi's profile with children listed: Gabriele, 10 years old (Boy) and Giada, 6 years old (Girl).

The 'Edit user profile' section displays three mobile app screens:

- Edit user profile:** Shows the 'Edit profile' form for Lucia Bianchi with fields for phone number, address, city, state, and email address.
- Edit user profile 2:** Shows the 'Edit profile' form for Lucia Bianchi with fields for phone number, address, city, state, and email address.
- Edit user profile 3:** Shows the 'Edit profile' form for Lucia Bianchi with fields for phone number, address, city, state, and email address.

The 'Men...' screen displays a menu with options: Export data, Delete data, and Sign out.

Children profile

The 'Children profile' section displays five mobile app screens:

- Children profile:** Shows the profile for Gabriele Bianchi, 10 years old (Boy), with parent Lucia Bianchi (Mother) and an 'ADD PARENT' button.
- Edit children pro...:** Shows the 'Edit profile' form for Gabriele Bianchi with fields for name, birthday, gender, and an 'Add specific information' button.
- Add child screen:** Shows the 'Add child' form with fields for name, birthday, gender, and an 'Add specific information' button.
- Add child 1:** Shows the 'Add child' form for Gabriele Bianchi with fields for name, birthday, gender, and an 'Add specific information' button.
- Add child 2:** Shows the 'Add child' form for Gabriele Bianchi with fields for name, birthday, gender, and an 'Add specific information' button.
- Add child 3:** Shows the 'Add child' form for Gabriele Bianchi with fields for name, birthday, gender, and an 'Add specific information' button.
- Add child 4:** Shows the 'Add child' form for Gabriele Bianchi with fields for name, birthday, gender, and an 'Add specific information' button.

Navigation drawer and FAQs

Invite members - Group Administrator

Create a group

Search a group

Group page

Create a new activity

View time slots and insert availabilities

Filter activities

Calendar of the g...

Info of an activity

Info of an activity...

Slots of an activity

Activities of the g...

Filter by - 2

Slots of the grou...

Slots of the grou...

Slots of the grou...

Filter by - 1

Slots of the grou...

Calendar management

